

Systemic Understanding: Summary Report on 15 Case Study Results

MATS Deliverable 3.5

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Summary

This summary report provides a synthesis of the 15 case study analyses and results, following a three-phase methodological approach. In phase one, it provides an overview of the case studies' main features, taking the key structural elements from D3.1. Methodological guidelines and reporting template into account. The second phase provides a systemic understanding of agricultural trade from different sustainability perspectives. The aim is to illustrate how the elements that explain the current situation behave within the food system – either as drivers or outcomes – under the environmental sustainability and human rights perspectives we set out to address from the Grant Agreement. Finally, the third phase identifies and selects those SDG indicators from the D2.1 *Set of indicators to assess the sustainability impacts of agricultural trade*, which are best suited to focus on the transformation of agricultural trade. This selection of indicators is done with a focus on their ability to help identify the key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights.

This summary and synthesis report is not only deemed useful for the following key processes and communication steps in subsequent MATS work packages (transition pathways development, policy recommendations development, society-stakeholder-policy dialogue, dissemination, and communication) but also useful as a blueprint for future research projects with a similar synthesis agenda.

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Lead Authors: Bustamante, M., Manrique, C., Vidueira, P.

Co-authors: Steiner, B.

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Introduction

Background and Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable provides a synthesis of the 15 case study analyses and results from a systems perspective, taking into account the work from previous work packages, tasks, and analysis work. In particular, it builds on the individual work and interconnections between (i) [D2.4 MATS Analytical framework](#) that was built upon [D2.1 SDG indicators for assessing the sustainability impacts of agricultural trade](#), [D2.2 Synthesis of model-based studies](#), and [D2.3 Sustainable Trade Toolbox](#), and (ii) the individual CS reports as main input, created following the [D3.1 CS Methodological guidelines and reporting template for the 15 cases studies in MATS](#). The overarching idea was to enable comparability in terms of analysis steps, methods, and results, in order to ensure high robustness of the derived results and recommendations while enabling transferable lessons across commodity, geographic, and other domains.

Within T3.3, we implemented follow-up meetings and briefing sessions with CS teams to support them during implementation and reporting. For this purpose, we also used the data pool and insights from the normalizing work in the [D3.4 Common data pool on sustainability standards and competitiveness](#). The *CS common reporting template* and a *CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of the Systems Approach* were the main guidance documents shared at the beginning of the process. These were shared while highlighting the relevance of D3.1. and D3.4. for comparability and consistency among CS in following implementation steps (fieldwork, analysis) and reporting.

Thereby, by distinguishing these documents with guiding instructions, we obtained both individual CS and joint CS contributions to WP3, thereby serving the overall MATS systemic ambitions.

Beyond what was envisaged in the Grant Agreement, we have aimed to work together with Trade4SDG and VC4Dev (details in the corresponding section) on several case studies, to benefit from synergies and joint transferable policy lessons with a systems perspective in mind.

Systems thinking

Adopting a food systems approach serves as a guiding principle to illuminate the intricate linkages between agricultural trade, markets, agricultural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being. This approach provides a systemic lens, revealing elements and interrelations that are crucial for understanding agricultural trade within food systems, addressing their main challenges, and fostering the positive and reducing the negative impact of trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being.

This systemic view of agricultural trade lays the foundation for stakeholders engaged in case studies to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the linkages mentioned above. To translate this perspective into actionable steps, we employed *the [D2.4 MATS Analytical Framework](#)*.

The MATS case studies applied the Analytical Framework following the [D3.1 Methodological guidelines and reporting template for the 15 case studies in MATS](#), which was discussed and reinforced with (i) in-person interactions as part of the workshops held in Maastricht (October 2022) and Moshi (October 2023) and (ii) additional guidance for the adoption of a systemic approach.

A pivotal tool to guide case studies in being systemic in their implementation and reporting was the *CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of the Systems Approach (see Appendix J)*. This table illustrates the steps and considerations CS should have in mind when doing a systemic analysis of the linkages between agricultural trade, markets, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being.

An enhanced *Common Reporting Template for MATS case studies* (see *Appendix K*) was built, in alignment with the *CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of the Systems Approach*, to guide case studies in the adoption of a food systems approach. Both documents were introduced and validated during the project meeting in Moshi in October 2023. The UPM team provided a comprehensive explanation for the practical application of both instruments, through an example, and gathered valuable feedback from MATS partners and CS leaders. The feedback was incorporated to refine and improve both instruments, making them more responsive, effective, and user-friendly.

Considering the feedback received from case studies during and after the Moshi meeting, the UPM team consolidated the MATS Agricultural Trade Systems Conceptual Framework, depicted in Figure 1. This framework showcases the contextual elements that act as drivers of the agricultural trade system's performance and dynamics and the elements that are impacted by it.

The structure of the Agricultural Trade System as in Figure 1 was translated into the *CS Guidance Table*, which included a list of relevant contextual elements and categorized them around policy and governance, human, social, environmental, and economic and markets dimensions. Using the *CS Guidance Table*, case study leaders and co-leaders selected the elements deemed relevant to express the issue addressed in their case studies and described the linkages between those elements and the agricultural trade. This structured approach aimed to ensure consistency across case studies, facilitating thematic and comparative analysis of the findings and results.

FIGURE 1. MATS AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM FRAMEWORK

Methodology

This section describes the methodological approach adopted to summarize the main findings of the MATS' fifteen case studies. Case studies 1 and 15 were each treated as two cases in their own rights in the analyses described below at the request of their leaders. CS 1 to differentiate the work and the insights obtained from the work done in Tanzania from that done in Uganda. And CS 15 to separate the two issues addressed. In other words, this deliverable treated MATS fifteen case studies as seventeen for practical purposes.

First, the work here builds on all previous deliverables in WP3, in particular on (i) [*D3.1 Methodological Guidelines and Reporting Template for the 15 Case Studies in MATS*](#) that was shared and discussed with all CS leaders and (ii) [*D3.4 Common data pool on sustainability standards and competitiveness*](#). Moreover, it builds on key deliverables on WP2 that end up being part of (ii) the [*D2.4 MATS Analytical Framework*](#).

Concerning the activities performed in WP3, the Project Advisory Group members and some key MATS partners were involved in the support and follow-up activities by reviewing and providing feedback at two critical moments of CS reporting – in the mid-term report and the final report.

For the mid-term report, key MATS partners were tasked with offering comments, suggestions, or any pertinent information concerning a designated section: template consistency; general view - Fit with MATS Grant Agreement; general approach/content; institutional, regulatory, and legal frameworks; transition pathways and policy recommendations; human rights perspective; systems inquiry and systems diagramming; and visualization - compatibility with the website. While feedback from some PAG members was received, it

was not mandatory.

Concerning the final report, all CS reports were sent to PAG members for content evaluation. A comprehensive table was crafted to assess the contents, focusing on the following issues:

- a) Complex interlinkages - How does the case study contribute to shedding light on the intricate connections between agri-food trade, sustainability, investments, and human well-being?
- b) Case study insights helping to move the agenda toward more sustainable agri-food trade, within its commodity/ regional/ SDG/ methods context.
- c) Systemic understanding: How and to what extent does CS contribute to developing a systemic understanding of agri-food trade?
- d) Governance & institutional structures and power imbalances: Does the CS discuss/address/reflect on governance structures and power imbalances?
- e) Regulatory & legal frameworks: Does the CS analyze, engage with, or reflect upon legal and institutional frameworks shaping agri-food trade?
- f) From a methods perspective, is the CS implemented rigorously?
- g) Is there anything else you believe is missing from the CS report?

The engagement, support, and feedback from MATS partners and PAG members to case studies contributed significantly to the results obtained in this deliverable.

Concerning the linkages with previous WPs, we highlight the foundations laid by the MATS Analytical Framework (Fig. 2) for developing, in WP3, key

guidance documents for case studies to implement a systemic approach to assessing linkages between agricultural trade, markets, agricultural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being around the globe; and to identify key leverage points to foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being.

FIGURE 2. MATS ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

Building on the methods, frameworks, and data milestones mentioned above, we followed a three-phase methodological approach, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Phase one aims to offer an overview of the case studies' main features. These features include location and agrifood products, trade scope and trade relations, CS objective, CS methodology, stakeholders' engagement, transition pathways information, and policy recommendations.

Phase two aims to provide a systemic understanding of agricultural trade by illustrating how the elements explaining its current situation behave within the food system. In this phase, case studies identify the elements within the political, human, social, environmental, economic, and market-related dimensions deemed relevant to the issue addressed. Later, case studies explore and describe the role of each element within the agricultural trade system, whether as drivers influencing the system's dynamics and performance or as impacts resulting from it. While describing the role of each element, case studies delve into their linkages with food value chain activities. The *Common Reporting Template for MATS case studies* and the *CS Guidance Table* are the two primary tools for case studies to systemically identify and describe key elements and linkages within the agricultural trade system from the environmental sustainability and human rights perspective set out under the Grant Agreement.

Finally, the third phase consolidates MATS case studies information on strategic actions (levers) and policy recommendations to move toward a sustainable agricultural trade, based on the identification of key elements that hold the potential to foster the positive and mitigate the negative impacts on environmental sustainability and human well-being. Moreover, this last phase illustrates the potential contributions of the levers of change to the Sustainable

Development Goals, particularly to those SDG indicators from the [*D2.1 Set of indicators for assessing the sustainability impacts of agricultural trade*](#), which are best suited to focus on the necessary effective transformation of agricultural trade.

The findings from this Deliverable, particularly those from the third phase of analysis, feed into MATS' work on WP5, which derive transition pathways for desirable changes in trade relations and instruments and formulate policy recommendations.

This deliverable also takes synergies and insights into account that were created with Trade4SDG and VC4Dev interactions. In particular, two cases were found to apply to the same regional and commodity context in both consortia: the case of Ghana (where our MATS partner UPM exchanged with Trade4SDG partner CSIR-Science and Technology Policy Research Institute) and the case of Tunisia (where our MATS partner TNI exchanged with Trade4SDG partner CREA - Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria). Furthermore, MATS CS#2 (oats) cooperated with VC4Dev, by applying the VC4Dev social matrix profile to the MATS oats case study (a novelty, since thus far, this social profile had only been used in the developing economies, not developed economies context, here Finland).

The following sections describe the three phases of our analysis in more detail before providing a synthesis and conclusions. Phases two and three are organized into three levels to summarize the case studies' findings.

At the first level, we analyze each case study individually, delving into their specific contexts to understand the unique dynamics and particularities of each agricultural trade scenario.

In the second level, we group the case studies according to common features – such as similar issues, agrifood products, or geographical locations – and perform aggregated analyses to discuss the findings for each group. This allows us to identify patterns and insights that emerge within these focused groupings.

Finally, at the third level, we present the findings from the entire set of 15 MATS case studies collectively. This holistic view helps us to draw broader conclusions about agricultural trade and sustainability across diverse contexts.

This approach ensures that we thoroughly understand the specific contexts of each case study before aggregating them into thematic or territorial groupings, and ultimately into the complete set of MATS 15 case studies.

FIGURE 3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Phase I: Case Studies Overview

Step 1: Summarize the key information and features of the 15 MATS case studies.

This step provides an overview of the MATS case studies, illustrating how their diversity sets the groundwork for obtaining valuable and transferable insights on the linkages between the agricultural trade, markets, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being around the globe.

We present an overview of the case studies in terms of seven key attributes as detailed below:

Location and agrifood product (commodity) traded: A map figure was used to indicate the countries where MATS case studies are located, and the products traded in each.

Trade scope and trade relations: A map figure was used to indicate if CSs focus on domestic or international trade and to visualize import-export relationships when applicable.

Case studies objectives: The diversity of case studies – particularly in the issues they address and the goals they pursue – is considered one of MATS' main strengths. In that sense, CS objectives were analyzed in terms of the drivers and/or impacts of agricultural trade being addressed in the five dimensions of MATS' analytical framework to illustrate their contributions to understanding the linkages between agricultural trade and markets, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights from a systems perspective.

Case studies methodology: The methods/ tools used by CS were grouped into twelve categories (See Table 1 in the results section), which allowed us to identify CSs using similar instruments, methods, and approaches during their implementation. Considering each instrument's primary goal, we selected to which stage(s) contribute to (i) data collection and analysis, (ii) exploration of the linkages that make sense of the situation addressed, or (iii) exploration of potential transition pathways and formulation of policy recommendations.

Stakeholders' engagement: We indicate in which stages(s) of the CS implementation stakeholders were engaged, whether in (i) data collection and analysis, (ii) exploration of the linkages that make sense of the situation addressed, or (iii) exploration of potential transition pathways and formulation of policy recommendations.

Step 2: Grouping of case studies

All the information summarized in Step 1 revealed commonalities among CS upon which meaningful CS groups were identified.

For geographical location, CS were grouped into four categories, following the SDG regions defined by the UN (<https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/regional-groups/>): Northern Africa and Western Asia; Sub-Saharan Africa; Europe and Northern America; and Latin America and the Caribbean.

For trade scope and relationships, CS were grouped into five groups, following the UN GeoScheme: Those focused on domestic trade (incl. regional markets like ECOWAS, etc.) and those that have their primary trade relations with Europe, North America, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Eastern Asia.

For objectives/issues addressed, CS were grouped by the linkages (drivers and impacts) where each focus.

Phase II: Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

This phase summarizes the findings of the systemic analysis of the elements and linkages explaining the agricultural trade under environmental sustainability and human well-being perspectives.

Step 3: Identify elements addressed by MATS case studies to obtain a systemic view of the agricultural trade.

The basis for a systemic understanding of agricultural trade is to identify the elements that affect trade and are affected by it ([D1.1 Linkages between agricultural trade, markets, investments, environmental sustainability, and human well-being](#)). Using a food systems approach, we built a list of elements considered relevant to (i) understand the linkages between the agricultural trade, markets, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being and (ii) shed light on leverage points in agricultural trade systems that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts on environmental sustainability and human well-being.

This comprehensive list of elements was shared, discussed, and strengthened with MATS partners, case studies leaders, and co-leaders. The enhanced list of elements set the groundwork for case studies - being aware of the complexity of agricultural trade - select those deemed relevant as evaluating linkages across stages of the agrifood value chain and the five dimensions of the MATS Agricultural Trade conceptual framework.

The selection of elements was made through an iterative approach carried out collaboratively among case studies leaders, co-leaders, and the UPM team. The UPM team guided case studies teams to identify those elements acting as Drivers and Impacts of the Agricultural Trade in their specific contexts. Understanding drivers as those elements that affect the food system activities (from production to consumption) and impacts as those being affected by the food system activities. The resulting narrative about the linkages within the Agricultural Trade Systems in each case study was shared with the UPM team.

Based on the CS final reports, the UPM team proposed some modifications or additions to the narratives shared by the case studies. These proposed changes were discussed with the case studies' teams through Zoom meetings and collaborative Excel documents. The objective of this collaborative process was to reflect as accurately as possible the dynamics and performance of the agricultural trade system in each case study. This selection was made within a more profound exploratory-analytical procedure guided by the *CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of a Systems Approach*, which will be explained in Step 4.

Given the extensive number of elements proposed, we created an intermediate layer (group) named "topics" within each dimension, to ease the analyses proposed in Phase II (see Appendix A for details).

As detailed below, the identification and analysis of the elements influencing and influenced by agricultural trade are part of the **first, second, and third-level analyses** presented in this Deliverable.

First Level – CS individual analysis

At the first level of our analysis, we explore the drivers and impacts of agricultural trade within each CS, organized and aggregated by topics. To provide a systemic understanding of the linkages between the agricultural trade, markets, investments, environmental sustainability, and human rights and well-being, the CSs rank the degree of influence that drivers have over the various agrifood value chain activities and the impact of those activities on various elements within the five dimensions of the MATS Agricultural Trade conceptual framework.

The degree of influence ranking was informed by the case studies' narratives about the dynamics and performance of the agricultural trade system, built on the previously identified linkages. While a more comprehensive analysis of linkages between contextual elements and the agrifood value chain activities is detailed in Step 4, we employ spider/radar charts that visually represent the degree of influence each contextual element exerts on the agricultural trade system (Drivers) and, conversely, the degree of influence that the agricultural trade system has over them (Impacts).

The spider/radar charts were crafted by averaging the designated degree of influence for each linkage (driver or impact) between the agrifood value chain stages and the contextual elements. The results were then aggregated by topics, providing a more concise and insightful illustration, and a basis for identifying leverage points.

Second Level – Group analysis

In the second level of our analysis, we explore the drivers and impacts of the agricultural trade system addressed by MATS case studies, organizing them

based on (i) their objective or main issue addressed, and (ii) geographical location.

To present these findings, we use donut charts illustrating the number of case studies addressing each element – whether a driver or an impact – aggregated by topics within each dimension (Figure 9 to 15, in the results section).

Considering the groups defined around the two CS attributes mentioned above, we performed the analysis for the following:

- i. Objective/ Main issue addressed: (a) Governance and trade regimes for sustainable development and human rights, (b) Social and human rights considerations for sustainable agricultural trade, (c) Power imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths.
- ii. CS location: (a) Northern Africa and Western Asia, (b) Sub-Saharan Africa, (c) Europe and Northern America, (d) Latin America and the Caribbean.

Third Level – Overall analysis of the 15 case studies

We examine how the set of 15 MATS case studies engages with diverse elements influencing and influenced by agricultural trade. This analysis reveals the number of case studies that address specific elements, allowing us to identify the most and least commonly explored elements within the MATS context. Moreover, this first-level analysis offers a comprehensive overview of the drivers and impacts of agricultural trade that MATS case studies delve into.

Although the MATS case studies are not representative of the world's agricultural trade situation, they do cover a wide range of issues, agrifood products, and trade relations that are worth exploring. Analyzing the frequency with which certain elements are addressed by the set of MATS case studies illustrates their relative relevance as drivers or impacts of the agricultural trade within that set.

Our analyses adhere to the three layers of the MATS analytical framework: Dimensions, topics, and elements.

- i. Dimensions: We illustrate the frequency with which elements within each dimension are addressed by the set of MATS case studies. It is important to clarify that, since each dimension comprises several elements, the count presented in the diagrams represents the sum of case studies that address the various elements included in each dimension. Although some case studies may refer to a particular element multiple times to convey distinct facets of the issue addressed (e.g., "Power relations and imbalances" in CS8), our count focuses on the overall presence or absence of each element in the context of each case study.

The resulting diagrams reflect the cumulative frequency addressed by the set of MATS case studies within each of the five dimensions.

Through a spider web visualization (Fig. 16, in the results section), we offer a comprehensive overview of the distribution of elements addressed by dimensions, irrespective of whether they function as drivers or impacts of the agricultural trade system. Additionally, we generate a bar chart (Fig. 17, in the results section) detailing the frequency with which elements within each dimension act as drivers and/or are impacted by the agricultural trade in the set of MATS case studies.

- ii. Topics: To further refine our analysis, in this layer, we show the frequency of elements addressed by the case studies within each topic, differentiating them by their roles in the agricultural trade system like drivers or impacts (Fig. 18, in the results section). Compared with the earlier dimension-based analysis, this approach allows for a more detailed examination, offering insights into the frequency of elements addressed within each topic, specifically as drivers or impacts.
- iii. Elements: We employ a heatmap to provide a comprehensive portrayal of how MATS case studies address specific elements (Table 4, in the results section). This method allows us to showcase the number of CS tackling each element, further distinguishing between drivers and impacts.

Step 4: Describe the linkages between agricultural trade and its embedding context under a systems perspective.

Following the identification of elements addressed by MATS case studies in Step 3, we focus on the linkages between the agrifood value chain and its embedding context (see Figure 4). This involves examining the role that contextual elements play as drivers or impacts of the agricultural trade system.

FIGURE 4. FAO SUSTAINABLE FOOD VALUE CHAIN FRAMEWORK

As detailed in Step 3, CS leaders and co-leaders significantly contributed to gaining a systemic understanding of agricultural trade by identifying and exploring key elements and linkages within their respective case studies. This process was facilitated by a series of Zoom meetings, ongoing communication regarding the [D3.1 Reporting template for the 15 case studies in MATS](#), and the implementation of the *CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of a Systems Approach*. CS leaders and co-leaders exchanged insights on the linkages between agricultural trade and its embedding context, including politics, governance and regulations, human dimension, social dimension, environmental dimension, and economy and markets (see Fig. 1).

To show the degree of influence of contextual elements over the agrifood value chain activities and vice versa, we proposed a categorization with four values:

- 4 – Fundamentally affects
- 3 – Severely affects
- 2 – Moderately affects
- 1 – Somehow affects

The valuation of linkages was carried out by the teams working on the case studies, based on the extensive knowledge gathered during their implementation. This process was methodologically guided by the UPM team as part of the exploration and interpretation of the linkages that determine the dynamics of the agricultural trade system.

As detailed below, exploring linkages is part of the **first and second-level analyses** presented in this Deliverable.

First Level – CS individual analysis

At the CS individual level, we present the linkages between the four activities of the agrifood value chain – agricultural production, processing, trade and retail, and consumption – and the multidimensional context, showing which elements act as drivers and which are impacted by the different stages of the agrifood value chain and to what extent (degree of influence).

To present the results of this level of analysis, we draw heavily on the TEEBAgriFood framework (see Figure 5 below).

Second Level – Grouping Analysis

At the second level of our analysis, we explore linkages in the agricultural trade system by aggregating the results of case studies sharing key attributes such as (i) objective or main issue addressed, and (ii) geographical location.

The approach used to illustrate linkages involves computing a group average value of the degree of influence of each driver and the impact explored in the case studies. Subsequently, we average the group values by topic to present a more synthesized and informative diagram. The resulting values express the degrees of influence of each linkage addressed by MATS CS within each group, aggregated by topics.

The outcome is a comprehensive double-entry table by group, providing insights into the nature of linkages – whether drivers or impacts – and their respective degrees of influence on the four stages of the value chain.

FIGURE 5. LINKS BETWEEN FOUR CAPITAL AND THE ECO-AGRI-FOOD VALUE CHAIN (SOURCE: TEEB, 2018).

Phase III: Insights to move toward a sustainable agricultural trade (transition pathways).

Step 5: Summarize individual CS-based information on potential pathways to foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being.

In this step, we consolidate the information provided by individual CS on strategic actions (levers) and policy recommendations to move toward a sustainable agricultural trade. This process involves identifying key elements within agricultural trade systems – i.e., leverage points – that hold the potential to foster positive and mitigate negative impacts on environmental sustainability and human well-being.

Our focus on synthesizing potential transformation pathways is dedicated to understanding how, by capitalizing on the identified leverage points, agricultural trade may actively contribute to achieving Sustainable Development Goals.

First Level – Individual analysis

We explored the contextual particularities of each case study from a systems perspective to identify strategic interventions to accelerate transformation processes toward sustainable agricultural trade.

The first step in proposing actions to contribute to the transformation of agricultural trade systems was to identify the elements with the potential to trigger system-wide changes. We developed a brief narrative around each case study to illustrate the essential role of certain elements as leverage points

to make the agricultural trade systems more sustainable.

Based on the identified leverage points, we proposed strategic actions or levers for transforming the agricultural trade system, taking into account the specific context of each case study to distill valuable insights and knowledge. Additionally, we shared policy recommendations that emerged from the exploration of actions for change and transition pathways.

Third Level – Overall analysis

We synthesized the main transition pathways that arise from the set of MATS case studies. The leverage points, which are elements with the potential to trigger systemic changes, are organized into the five dimensions of the MATS Agricultural Trade conceptual framework to illustrate the value of the CS-specific transition pathways information from a systems perspective, before sharing this information further as part of the visioning and transition pathways development and analysis (WP5).

Step 6: Identify the potential contributions of MATS CS-derived strategic actions or levers to the SDGs.

First Level – Individual analysis

Case study leaders and co-leaders selected - from the *Common list of SDG indicators* defined collectively during the design of the MATS analytical framework in Work Package 2 (D2.1) - at least three SDG indicators that align with the focus, scope, and emerging results of their case studies.

At this level of analysis, we list the SDG indicators highlighted by each case study, including indicators outside the Common List defined within the MATS Grant Agreement that were considered relevant during their implementation. In this way, we illustrate how MATS case studies, by proposing and developing strategic actions for sustainable agricultural trade, contribute to advancing the SDGs.

Furthermore, we used AI (<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) to individually characterize each CS in terms of SDG prevalence, as well as apply the AI tool to the final synthesis report to provide additional visual robustness checks (see Appendix I).

Third Level – Overall analysis of the 15 case studies

To provide an overview of the links between the MATS case studies and the SDGs, we developed donut charts displaying the number of CS that address each of the indicators identified as relevant or pertinent to MATS (captured in the list of common indicators in the Grant Agreement).

We organized the findings by contextual dimension to show their systemic distribution. In addition, we linked the indicators to each of the 16 SDGs using

a color code to show how certain SDGs have indicators related to more than one dimension. For example, SDG2 Zero Hunger is linked to the political, human, and economic dimensions, as shown in Figure 20 in the results section.

Results

Overview of MATS Case Studies

We begin the results section by providing an overview of the key attributes of MATS case studies.

Figure 6 shows the location and the agrifood products traded in MATS case studies. The case studies are mainly concentrated in Africa, followed by Europe, Latin America, and finally, North America, covering a wide diversity of agrifood products.

Figure 7 shows the trade relations between countries and regions, revealing a clear trend towards export relations to and intra-Europe. Also noteworthy are the trade relations within some areas of the African continent.

FIGURE 6. CASE STUDIES LOCATION AND PRODUCT

FIGURE 7. CASE STUDIES TRADE RELATIONSHIPS

Figure 8 shows the diversity of objectives addressed by the case studies and how each of them delves into the different linkages within the agricultural trade system. The MATS case studies mainly address how elements linked to policy and governance and economics and markets act as drivers in the agricultural trade system, impacting particularly human, social, and environmental dimensions. Figure 8 provides an overview of the linkages between contextual elements and the agrifood value chain (drivers) and vice versa (impacts). To facilitate the analysis, we use a color code to differentiate the linkages between the five dimensions of the agricultural trade system. We also use the numerical coding of the case studies to show which case studies address which linkages.

FIGURE 8. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES OBJECTIVES FROM A SYSTEMS PERSPECTIVE.

Table 1 provides an overview of the methods and tools addressed by the MATS case studies. This table shows that secondary “data review and analysis” and “key informant/stakeholder interviews” were the most commonly used instruments among the case studies, followed by causal loop diagrams. Notably, most of the instruments were used for data collection and analysis, as well as the exploration of linkages, and only a few supported discussions on potential transition pathways and the formulation of policy recommendations.

Table 2 gives an idea of the degree of participation and engagement of agricultural trade stakeholders in the MATS case studies. This table shows that in most case studies, stakeholders were involved in the stages of data collection and analysis and linkage exploration, to a lesser degree, in formulating policy recommendations and discussing potential transition pathways.

TABLE 1. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES METHODS AND TOOLS

Methods/ Tools		Number of CS		Purpose		
				Data collection & analysis	Exploration of linkages (Drivers - Impacts)	Impact pathways information and policy recommendations
Causal Loop Diagram		7			7	7
Economic Analysis	Gross margin analysis for farm profitability	4	2	2		
	Typical farm methodology		2	2		
Fieldwork/ On-farm visits		3		3		
Focus Group Discussions		5		4	4	2
Key informant/stakeholder interviews		13		11	5	2
Participatory workshop		2		1	2	2
Secondary data review and analysis	Literature review	15	10	10	2	
	Analysis of secondary data		4	4	3	
	Desk research		2	2		
	Analysis of database		1	1		
	Statistical review		2	1		
	Statistical system and accounting matrix		1	1	1	
Surveys		6		5	2	
Soft systems Methodology		1		1	1	1
Text/Content Analysis	Content analysis	4	2	2		
	Controversy scann		1	1		
	Text analysis using ITC's Standards Map Tool		1	1	1	
Value chain mapping		2		2	2	
Modelling methods	Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)	5	1	1	1	1
	Spatial Analysis		2	2	2	2
	Systems Dynamics		1	1	1	1
	Simplified commodity chain models and simulations		1		1	1
	Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)-based multiplier analysis		1	1	1	

TABLE 2. OVERVIEW OF STAKEHOLDERS' PARTICIPATION DURING CASE STUDIES IMPLEMENTATION

CS	Stakeholders' engagement			
	Data collection & analysis	Exploration of linkages (Drivers - Impacts)	Impact pathways information	Policy recommendations
Total				
1a	x	x	x	x
1b	x	x		
2	x	x		x
3				
4	x	x	x	x
5	x	x	x	x
6	x	x		
7	x	x		x
8	x	x		
9	x	x		x
10	x	x		
11	x			
12	x	x	x	x
13	x	x		
14	x	x	x	x
15a	x			
15b	x			
	+ 11 CS	7-10 CS	4-6 CS	1-3 CS

Grouping of Case Studies

Based on the analysis of attributes, MATS case studies were grouped according to the objectives or issues addressed, the location, and the trade relationships, as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3. GROUPS OF CASE STUDIES BY KEY ATTRIBUTES

Groups	Description	CS
1. Objectives	Governance and trade regimes in support of sustainable development and human rights.	1a, 1b, 4, 5, 7, 8, 15b, 3
	Social & human rights considerations for Sustainable Agricultural Trade.	2, 10, 12, 13, 11
	Power imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths.	6, 14, 15a, 9
2. Location (UN SDG re-regions)	Northern Africa and Western Asia	15a, 15b
	Sub Saharan Africa	1a, 1b, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12
	Europe and Northern America	2, 3
	Latin America and the Caribbean	8, 14
3. Trade relationships	Domestic trade (incl. regional markets)	2, 3, 4, 5
	Europe	1a, 1b, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 15a, 15b
	Eastern Asia (China)	14

Agricultural trade from a systems perspective

Delve into the particularities of MATS case studies to explore linkages between agricultural trade and sustainability dimensions.

The following factsheets offer a brief description of each case study, presenting contextualized evidence on the linkages between agricultural trade and sustainability dimensions. Each factsheet provides insights into the interrelationships between agri-food value chain activities and the political, social, human, environmental, and economic context. This approach highlights key findings from each case study while acknowledging their unique, context-specific characteristics.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Objective

- i. Assess the **impact of government measures, international standards, and trade regimes and practices** at local, national, and international levels, on **reducing poverty** among smallholder farmers.
- ii. Assess the **adoption of Fair Trade and Human Rights considerations** for attaining **SDG 1 Poverty, 2 Hunger, 3 Health, 5 Gender Equality, 13 Climate action**.
- iii. Explore **implications of power inequality, participation, and public interests** in pricing.

Methods

- Economic analysis
- Focus group discussions
- Key informants' interviews

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The interplay of public and private institutions** shapes the **power dynamics**, **operational efficiency**, and **market interactions** within the Uganda’s coffee sector.
 - Public institutions provide essential support through regulation, research, extension services, and quality assurance, creating enabling conditions for the coffee sector’s sustainable development.
 - Private actors, including input dealers, farmers’ organizations, aggregators, and exporters, drive the value chain’s activities and dynamics. International commercial entities control downstream segments, working with other value chain actors to ensure quality and efficiency. Aggregators buy and dry coffee from scattered farmers, while processors add value before selling to exporters. Middlemen dominate local markets by offering instant cash and reducing transaction costs for farmers.
- ✓ **Bureaucratic process of inspection and certification at national level** – linked to a limited quality control infrastructure - **limits the growth of Uganda’s coffee export business**.
- ✓ There is some **misunderstanding and discomfort among value chain actors concerning some provisions in the regulatory frameworks** that prioritize the coffee value chain, **which prevent their enforcement**.
 - Particularly, provisions concerning farmers’ registration to ease traceability and legal licences and subscription fees to associations and export companies.
- ✓ There is **power asymmetry between buyers from developed countries and producers from developing countries**, **which affects farmers’ return**.
 - As there is no minimal or direct intervention in the coffee markets at the farm gate, the price deviation due to high access costs between the farm gate and the export markets directly affect the farmer’s return on coffee.
 - Unless the constraints faced by farmers are addressed, the actors at a higher level of the value chain will continue to reap more from the coffee business.
- ✓ **The participation of profit-oriented actors along the value chain limits information transparency**
- ✓ **Digitalization** along the coffee value chain is still low but holds an **interesting potential to improve businesses performance, foster farmers’ financial inclusion, support the uptake of agricultural practices and skills development, and increase transparency and visibility of farmers into last mile operations**.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Coffee associations** advocate for a **favourable policy environment**, support coffee production through **information sharing and training**, **support trade expansion**, and **foster the development of market linkages under different schemes** (e.g., Fairtrade, Organic, Rainforest Initiatives).
- ✓ **Measures that promote and accelerate integration among value chain** – through both horizontal and vertical linkages – would help them to **enhance production efficiency, products’ quality and safety, reach better prices, and contribute to environmental sustainability and poverty reductions**.
- ✓ **Social norms and structures, gender-specific constraints, and discrimination issues shape the social dynamics of the coffee system.**
 - Coffee is largely produced by men, while youth and women work either as supporting family members or as casual employees, which contributes to unequal distribution of resources and benefits within the value chain.
 - Women have comparatively less access to land, credit, and information than men, which limits their participation and benefits from the coffee system.
 - Labour is a major constrain for women farmers, who have to divide time for intra-household chores, and do not afford waged labor.
 - Traditional gender roles and social structures limit women’s involvement in planning and decisionmaking within the value chain.
- ✓ **Occupational health disparities, declining youth participation, and child involvement in Uganda’s Coffee Sector.**
 - Employees downstream enjoy safer working environments due to regulatory standards, while limited hazard awareness hampers farmers’ occupational health.
 - Youth involvement in coffee farming is declining, posing a risk to the sector’s future.
 - According to coffee actors, children are inevitably involved in production activities, but largely for character building and skill development.
- ✓ **Climate change adaption measures such as coffee shading, mulching, manure application, and irrigation practices are promoted in Uganda’s coffee system to contribute to environmental sustainability.**
- ✓ **The agro-industrialization agenda to add value on coffee** for better earning create unique platforms for the **better share of coffee prices**, and hence, **better incomes and livelihoods coinciding with poverty reduction**.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Trade agreements boost Uganda’s coffee exports and linkages with Multinational Corporations (MNC) but increase farmers’ price volatility risk.**
 - Trade agreements positively impact coffee production, export performance, and linkage with MNCs, with trade values rising 80% for countries that belong to Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) and 182% for East African Community (EAC) countries.
 - Trade liberalization exposes farmers to international price volatility, unlike the former system of fixed prices by cooperatives and local traders.
- ✓ **The EU stringent non-tariff measures** (Sanitary and Phytosanitary measures, and Technical Barriers to Trade) **continue to affect coffee trade, depriving value chain actors the opportunity of earning fair values and participating competitively in international markets.**
- ✓ **Institutional governance plays a crucial role in fostering certification standards in Uganda’s Coffee System**
 - Several organizations support coffee production by sharing information on good agronomic practices, market linkages, and promoting standards such as Fairtrade, Organic, and Rainforest certifications.
 - Despite the promotion and support, Fairtrade adoption is low among smallholder farmers due to high certification costs and weak institutional governance, leading to prevalent individual operations.
- ✓ **Coffee production as a pathways to poverty reduction and household income enhancement in Uganda**
 - Coffee production significantly contributes to household incomes in Uganda, providing over 50% of cash income for coffee farming households by 2017/2018. Despite a significant number of coffee farming households still live below the poverty level, coffee production remains a viable livelihood strategy capable of lifting many out of poverty.
 - Medium-scale farmers tend to achieve higher returns compared to small-scale farmers, and overall, coffee producers fare better in terms of income compared to non-coffee producers.
- ✓ **Coffee production contributes to enhance households welfare and increases their ability to cover basic needs and rights.**
 - Coffee production has the potential to increase per adult equivalent consumption expenditure by 13% and total consumption expenditure by 16%.
 - Coffee sales provide cash income that can be used to purchase food and cover other household expenses.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Key linkages between agrifood trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human wellbeing perspective

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Objective

- i. Assess the impacts of **trade regimes and practices** at local, national, and international levels on **reducing poverty among smallholder farmers**.
- ii. Assess the adoption of Fair Trade and human rights considerations for attaining **SDG 1,2,3,5,13**.
- iii. Analyze **government measures and international standards** that have a bearing on poverty reduction among smallholder farmers.
- iv. Explore the effects of **profitability** on **smallholder farmers' incomes and poverty reduction**.

Methods

- Economic analysis
- Focus group discussions
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Surveys
- Text/content analysis
- Value chain mapping

Stakeholders' engagement

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

- Policy and governance
- Social capital
- Human capital
- Economy and markets
- Environmental capital

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Good governance structures within a value chain** are essential to its long-term sustainability.
 - At the government side, much has already been done including establishment of the coffee industry stabilization fund, a coffee research institute, free coffee seedling production, distribution, promotion of cooperative institutions and public-private partnership in the coffee industry and creation of a political will for the development of the coffee sector, among others.
- ✓ **The Tanzanian government strives for increased agricultural productivity and profitability through transformative measures, emphasizing technological investments and efficient marketing systems.**
- ✓ **Deforestation and afforestation policies** affect **land use change**
 - Tanzania coffee production can result in risk of deforestation only when opening new farms, especially by estates.
 - Estate coffee farmers are opening new farms mainly by clearing forests or cutting down shade trees in previous coffee farms which have been abandoned by cooperatives.
- ✓ **Due Diligences obligations, government checks and penalties for not complying with EU regulations** affects **coffee production**.
 - The new EU regulation on deforestation free coffee will have an impact on availability of coffee from developing countries to EU.
- ✓ **Most Tanzanian coffee farmers face challenges with low production, attributed to a lack of improved varieties, high production costs from pest control, low quality, and international market prices.**
 - Tanzania's limited presence in global exchange markets, where coffee prices are determined, exacerbates the crop's low profitability
- ✓ **One of the major challenges affecting coffee production is the poor extension service.**
 - On the smallholder farmers level, less than half of the respondents of the study were aware on the international fair-trade, its standards and expected benefits.
- ✓ **Estate farm managers understand and exercise their responsibility of safeguarding labour rights for their employees.**
 - They understand that making labour rights one of their main agenda in day-to-day operations is crucial to enhance employees' willingness to be committed to their work and deliver the required output in the farms and processing units.
- ✓ **Smallholder farmers are not constrained with strict labour rights in their operations.**
 - On the side of smallholder farmers, the practice is different because they own small plots of land and grow coffee using household labour and, sometimes, community groupings between nearby families in the villages to help each other.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The lack of integration and synergy among actors in the coffee value chain does not allow all actors to participate in decision-making.**
 - Small-scale farmers are the least privileged. They often find decision-making spaces closed, especially concerning crucial matters like pricing and standards.
 - Collaboration expectations with banks and input suppliers are hindered by farmers' limited knowledge and negotiation power.
- ✓ **Farmers' limited knowledge of markets dynamics restrict their participation and agency.**
 - Smallholder farmers are less privileged in the sense that they cannot be fully participants of the market segment. This situation works in favor of the downstream actors who take advantage of this knowledge gap.
 - Each actor in the value chain appears to maximize own interests at the expense of smallholder farmers who continue to be abused.
- ✓ **Climate change has a negative impact** on coffee production.
 - Climate change has reduced availability of water for coffee production in Kilimanjaro area.
 - Droughts have become more common.
- ✓ **Farmers have strategies to reduce and prevent soil erosion**, such as planting trees in their farms and surrounding areas.
- ✓ **The high volumes of clean water needed for irrigation and during wet processing, together with the wastewater generated**, are critical environmental challenges of the coffee value chain.
- ✓ **Coffee is traded to exporters by Tanzania Coffee Board (TCB) through auctions at Moshi. Most of the prominent exporters are affiliated with the multinational corporations which sell coffee to roasters in consuming countries.**
 - Prices are usually set in reference to New York market for Arabica coffee and London futures market for Robusta coffee. On the other hand, in direct export market producers of best coffee that are able to create direct contact with buyers overseas are allowed to pass the auction and sell their coffee directly.
 - Most of coffee that is produced in Tanzania is exported and local consumption is estimated at only 7% of the overall production.
- ✓ **International market restrictions, quality standards, post-liberalization input challenges, subsidy withdrawals, and fluctuation prices** disadvantage small-scale farmers.
- ✓ **With market liberalization of the coffee sector, the dominance of cooperative unions in the coffee sector waned**, contrary to expectations, **resulting on a foreign businesses dominance.**
 - Liberalization produced mixed results. Farmers received a larger percentage of export prices, but the quality of coffee declined, allowing foreign businesses to dominate the industry.
 - The shift towards Private Coffee Buyers after liberalization eroded the economic foundation of cooperatives by reducing or eliminating the cooperatively provided services, thus leaving small-scale farmer vulnerable. Excessive control and political interference eroded members' morale, and cooperatives struggled to compete in the free market, leading to their disintegration.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Fair trade enhances farmers’ participation into the agricultural cooperatives and subsequent decision-making processes, enabling them to obtain better prices, incomes and profits after coffee exports.**
 - The income gained by coffee farmers through trading has the potential to cover their household food expenses for a year, pay school fees, buy farms, improve housing conditions and pay for medical services, hence improving the welfare of farmers households and reducing their poverty levels.
 - Coffee contributes almost 5% of Tanzania’s total exports and generates income averaging US\$100 million per year.
- ✓ **Despite its benefits, Fair Trade Programs frequently rest on a lack of understanding of the realities of production, resulting in a gap between producing and consuming countries.**
 - Fair trade programs were expected to provide guidance and ultimately benefits to smallholder farmers by making consumers pay price premiums to promote social and economic change and environmental sustainability.
- ✓ **Lack of transparency and information asymmetry are some of the factors inhibiting the realization of the benefits of fair-trade programs by smallholder farmers.**
 - Farmers get limited consideration for human rights at the lower end of the coffee value chain and also fail to enjoy the benefits of digitization in a modern world.
- ✓ **Despite the growing global demand for fair-trade coffee, production of fair-trade certified coffee has been declining, as seen in Tanzania.**
 - Estate farmers still reported that regulatory initiatives and the associated compliance with fair trade standards has proved to be highly costly to the extent that the price premiums received do not cover their costs effectively at all the times.
 - Estate farmers feel that they are overregulated in the whole process of complying with the certification standards right from the production stage, all of which cut off the eventual premium prices received.
 - Officials at the coffee estates told they have to pay multiple taxes at various stages of the coffee value chain. They must pay 5% of total sells as local government authority crop access, 0.3% of gross revenue as service levy and 30% as income tax, among others.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Intra-EU trade, resilience, and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics”

Objective

- i. Assess how **social sustainability** is viewed relative to **environmental sustainability** in the Nordic and Germany oats value chains.
- ii. Assess the resilience of the Nordic and Germany oats value chains to changing **governance structures**, **changing climate**, and **changing trade regimes and pricing conditions**.
- iii. To what extent **social sustainability measures** are relevant for the resilience of oats value chains and the sustainability of intra-EU trade in oats and oats products?

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Surveys
- Text/content analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Intra-EU trade, resilience, and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Organizational change is desirable (at processor and retailer level)** for the sustainability transition of the oat's VCs.
 - Social sustainability standards regarding labor are matters of HR departments, not part of companies' otherwise dedicated sustainability units.
 - Considering the difficulties of measuring social welfare of the personnel, reporting is naturally skewed in the direction of what's measurable and social aspects might end up receiving less attention.
- ✓ **Organizations that work with suppliers rely on codes of conduct, which outline requirements across various dimensions.**
 - By signing into the codes of conduct, suppliers pledge to follow those requirements, and the organizations trust that the suppliers comply.
- ✓ **Lack of transparency and poor working conditions at farm and processing level can lead to unfair competition in the oats value chain, resulting on a reduction of the market for small-scale farmer and reduced economic viability for small farms operations.**
- ✓ **Processors and retailers use their dominant position in relation to farmers to affect market prices in their favor (contract negotiations).**
 - Oats producers claim that there have been situations where a contract with a retailer has forced them to increase sustainability efforts in production
 - There is no market power or influence going from farmers upstream toward buyers.
- ✓ **Power imbalances of processors over producers result in changes in revenues at a level that is conducive to the continuation of operations for larger oats producers, but may be too low for small farmers.**
 - Reduction of the market for small farmers, and hence reduced economic viability for small farm operations.
- ✓ **There is a low representation of women in decisions on the purchase, sale, or transfer of assets.**
 - Low representation, such as their membership in farmer's organization, trade unions; and their representation in leadership positions within the organizations they are part of.
- ✓ **Farmers claim that F2F/ CAP sustainability requirements lower their competitiveness, and that greening payments are not enough to cover the costs from greening.**
- ✓ **Concerns about the transparency of the value chain and its implications for reporting.**
 - Not enough information is available from suppliers, so for example reporting on scope three emissions is not possible to the extent an organization might want.

“Intra-EU trade, resilience, and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Objective

- i. Estimate potential impacts of **policies that put a price on environmental and climate impacts**.
- ii. What are the **environmental and climate impacts** of Finnish regional dairy farming?
- iii. What are the **economic repercussions and income effects** of policy changes toward accounting environmental and climate impacts, on the regional **dairy production and agricultural households**?
- iv. How would Finnish dairy products compete if **the EU redesigns trade agreements** in a way that environmental and climate impacts are accounted for?

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Modelling methods
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

- Policy and governance
- Social capital
- Human capital
- Economy and markets
- Environmental capital

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

✓ **Through the Common Agricultural Policy, farms are granted subsidies for biodiversity protection.**

- In Finland, this support takes various forms, such as agri-environmental commitment support, farm modernization investments, and agricultural investment subsidies. These subsidies are versatile, covering areas like drainage, animal welfare, environmental improvements, building costs, and energy investments.
- Another subsidy available in Finland through pillar 2 of the CAP is animal well-being payments.
- Finnish agriculture is dependent of agricultural support that constitutes roughly one third of the farm incomes, over 90% of farms already participate in the EU's agri-environmental programmes and related measures. This has strengthened farmers' knowledge and skills to take into account environmental and climate issues in their farming practices.

✓ **Food safety standards regulate production, manufacture and trade.**

- Beyond EU regulations on animal traceability and holding place registration, additional national measures target animal diseases.
- Both the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and the Finnish Food Authority oversee national directives, tracking, and reporting on animal health.
- Finland's CAP plan recognizes animal diseases and antimicrobial resistance as risks to food safety and domestic food production stability.
- There are multiple third-party certifications in use throughout the Finnish, EU, and world markets, covering aspects such as food quality, production type, sustainability, and animal welfare.

✓ **Farm production in the EU needs to comply with environmental regulations such as enhanced conditionality in order to be entitled to agricultural support.**

- In the Finnish dairy sector, there are limitations to herd expansion in relation to: (a) manure application and (b) GHG emissions. Regulations on acceptable manure application per hectare and on GHG emissions impose a limit on the number of animals allowed.
- Revenues are supported by EU and national subsidies, currently based on the number of animals (and hence, also in this case there is no possibility to generate economies of scale).

✓ **Environmental and climate concerns have generated criticism for methane and nitrous oxide emissions, in addition to nutrient leakage caused by manure.**

- In the region, dairy producers own 50% of the grasslands (silage, hay and pasture) and 14% of the nature conservation fields. If dairy production becomes less competitive, other farms may produce crops in those present grasslands, which would increase emissions, especially in peat lands.
- En la actualidad, las turberas producen entre el 50% y el 60% de las emisiones climáticas de la agricultura finlandesa, aunque sólo el 10% de la superficie cultivada sean turberas. En Ostrobotnia del Norte, la proporción de turberas es mayor, un 29%.
- The carbon tax affected both dairy and other agricultural production based on their GHG emissions. Dairy production had a higher output/emission coefficient (2.37) compared to other agriculture (2.19)

✓ **Farmers' knowledge on environmental and climate impacts of dairy production supports sustainable production and acceptability of dairy farming among consumers.**

- Finland's CAP plan recognizes training and advisory services and the expansion of organic production as ways to maintain low antibiotic use and increase food production transparency and hygiene.

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Consumers are increasingly aware of -and interested in- environmental issues, which reduce the consumption of environmentally unsustainable dairy products.**
 - In Finland, transfer towards plant-based diets has been slowly begun especially among younger generations.
- ✓ **Despite numerous independent dairy farms in Finland, there are relatively few milk processors.**
 - The largest, Valio, produces approximately 85% of milk in Finland and has subsidiaries in the EU, the US, China, and Russia.
- ✓ **The significance of the dairy sector in North Ostrobothnia is evident in its local food processing industry.**
 - Dairy processing constitutes 43% of the food processing industries while Finnish national average is 16%.
 - Of the regional food exports, dairy products constitute 40%.
- ✓ **A decrease in local dairy production would significantly impact regional industries and household incomes.**
 - A change in consumer preferences, coupled with the possible implementation of a carbon tax, impacts both production costs and revenues. In such a scenario, a higher proportion of production is expected to be directed to export markets.
 - The Finnish dairy market faces intense competition within Europe and struggles to compete in terms of cost efficiency and brand attractiveness.
 - Low market prices increase farmers' dependence on agricultural support.
- ✓ **Because of the high production costs, Finnish agricultural products are not competitive in global markets.**
 - Profitability is also impacted by the fact that a higher number of animals carries higher costs (with a somewhat reduced possibility to create economies of scale in the Finnish context)
 - Norther location restricts crop production.
 - The Finnish dairy market faces fierce competition within Europe. And They are not competitive in terms of cost and brand attractiveness.

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Objective

- i. How **governments** can, **with support of the international community**, foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agri-food trade and trade policy regimes on **sustainable development and human rights**?
- ii. How **countries' trade regimes, local and international investments** into the agri-food value chain, and the adopted sustainability standards have impacted on socioeconomic and environmental conditions?
- iii. Identify key interventions in SSA countries to foster the **access of agri-food products to the EU and other international markets**.

Methods

- Focus group discussions
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Ethiopia, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania are signatories to the Malabo Declaration that commits members of the African Union to allocate at least 10% of the annual public budgetary resources to the agriculture sector.**
 - Only Ethiopia has managed to fulfill that; Ghana allocated between 5 and 6%; and Uganda and Tanzania allocated less than 4%.
- ✓ **Food policies and regulations that support the value chain of the commodities:**
 - In Ghana: Cocoa Development Board (COCOBOD) has provided subsidized services beyond extension and R&D by giving farmers new seedlings, farm equipment, fertilizers and chemicals, etc.
 - In Uganda: Banana VC, one challenge is the weak implementation of existing value chain improvement policies and strategies.
 - In Ethiopia: There are no specific policy statement to consider goat meat and goat milk as part of the food and nutrition security
 - In Tanzania: In Cassava VC, its only in the past five years the government prepared and adopted a policy to promote cassava as both a food crop and a cash crop for industrial use.
- ✓ **Ethiopia, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania and their respective agri-food products have in place institutional and legal frameworks to oversee compliance to social and environmental standards.**
 - In essence, they are drawn from internationally known and acceptable practices as spread headed by ILO (social norms), and the UNEP (environmental standards).
 - Social standards: Tanzania and Uganda have dedicated semi-autonomous public agencies established under the legislation that oversee Occupational Safety and Health. There is the Occupational Health and Safety Act of 2003 in Tanzania, and the Occupational Health and Safety Act (OSHA) of 2006 in Uganda. Ethiopia has legislations on labour health and safety since 1940s under the Department of Occupational Safety, Health and Working Environment. A similar arrangement prevail in Ghana where the Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations is directly responsible for overseeing compliance to the Labour Act.
 - All these countries have legislation that demand equal pay between men and women in same type of jobs and time worked and prohibit child labour.
 - In Cocoa VC, the compliance to labour laws that restrict the employment of children in cocoa picking is considered a challenge.
 - Environmental standards: Tanzania has the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC) established under NEM Act no.20 of 2004; Uganda has the National Environment Act (Cap 153); Ghana has the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) of 1994 under Act no.490.
- ✓ **Ethiopia, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania have policies and legislations on land that are friendly to the farming of the agri-food commodities.**
 - Tanzania: Land Use Policy of 2009 in place but still face challenges of conflicting usage between nomadic livestock pastoralists and crop farmers. Support is needed to the gigantic task of land use planning, surveying and titling of land parcels.
- ✓ **Ethiopia, Ghana, Uganda and Tanzania have interventions targeting the poor as part of social protection/welfare programs.**

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **From 2015 to 2021, the share of Bilateral ODA allocated to pro-poor sectors remained relatively stable between 60% and 80% for Tanzania, Uganda, and Ethiopia, while Ghana registered less than 60%.**
 - From the proportion allocated to productive sector, agriculture is the main designatory (2021):Tanzania 81%, Uganda 97%, Ethiopia 92%, Ghana 68%.a/media).
- ✓ **There is collaboration with development partners in resource mobilization as part of Overseas Development Assistance (ODA) be it loans or grants (e.g. World Bank, IFAD, and FAO) and research on crops and livestock - e.g. International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) (for cassava, banana and cocoa) and International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI) (for goats).**
 - There is still a need for increased funding to R&D to generate next level generation of breeds and varieties that can cope with climate change and changing consumer tastes.
- ✓ **The use of Good Agricultural Practices contribute to the sustainable use of territorial ecosystems.**
 - Tanzania: To meet increased export demand, cassava farmers require productivity enhancement rather than land area expansion, to avoid negative consequences of vegetation clearance in starting new farms.
 - Technologies that are environmentally friendly for the four agri-food commodities could be promoted for adoption by farmers (ridge-terracing to trap rainwater and drip irrigation for banana and cocoa, sub-soiling to retain more water per cassava plant, and paddock grazing of goats.)
- ✓ **Weak documentation of breeding, uncontrolled diseases, poor extension and veterinary services, and lack of appropriate infrastructure are among the most limiting factors that hampered the success of goat production.**
 - The efforts made to upgrade the stock of indigenous goats (with low productivity) is hampered by lack of sufficient and superior quality feeds and forages.
- ✓ **Weak linkages research-extension-farmers represent a barrier for the adoption of good practices that help VC agents to improve their yields and cost efficiency and comply with the standards to access national and international markets.**
- ✓ **Farmers’ limited capacity to invest in sustainable technologies hinders their ability to meet voluntary sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) and sustainability standards (VSS).**
 - Unsupportive rural and/or agricultural financing system, characterized by unsustainable prices credit facilities.
 - The difficulties faced by producers and processors in accessing research and extension services, processing and post-harvest handling infrastructure, among others resulting from unfavorable and unpredictable national marketing policies, have hampered their ability to invest in upgrading and using appropriate and sustainable technologies and practices.
 - Poor supportive rural infrastructure for transportation and post-harvest handling. In Goats VC, trekking of animals due to poor roads, and lack of fattening infrastructure before sale, resulted in weakened animals that fetch low selling prices.

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **There are traditionally established working norms at family level of labour division.**
 - Women and school-age children are expected to perform tasks such as peeling cassava and banana, tending young goats, and removing cocoa beans from their pods.
 - Traditions also restrict the transfer ownership of land considered ancestral or family land to women, thus disadvantaging them from owning land and using it as collateral to access financial products.
- ✓ **Poverty prevalence is higher in rural areas compared to urban areas.**
 - In all four countries, at least one third of the population lives below the \$1.99 poverty line.
 - Goats are used as a form of financial savings, thus providing some assurance of family survival in times of agricultural failures.
 - The Human Development Index (HDI) (combining health, education, shelter, income, etc) is above 0.5 for three countries of Uganda (0.544), Tanzania (0.549), Ghana (0.632). Ethiopia has the lowest HDI (0.498) among the four countries.
- ✓ **Commodities play a crucial role as staple foods for families, enhancing food security and nutrition by meeting essential dietary needs.**
- ✓ **The main impacts of climate change experienced in the four countries include increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as heat waves, droughts, floods, and tropical cyclones.**
- ✓ **Promoting goat meat trade will be continued or increased emission of GHG from livestock production.**
 - The agriculture sector accounts for about 74% of total national GHG emissions, with over 60% coming from livestock.
- ✓ **Cassava, goat, cocoa, and banana have a high potential for income generation through trade that provides fair returns to farmers' efforts.**
 - Tanzania: Cassava, as other smallholder food crops, assumes a dual role as a basic food item for families and as a source of income.
 - Ethiopia: Promoting goat/ goat meat trade is likely to contribute to family incomes in rural areas, especially in places that are not well suitable for ordinary crop farming given the drought resilience of goats.
 - Ghana: Cocoa crops assure the owner of a continuous stream of income for a long period of time.
 - Uganda: Banana can be grown in almost one half of the country thus positively impacting on incomes and livelihoods of most smallholder farmers. Like cassava, the crop doubles as a staple food item and for earning incomes from sale.
- ✓ **There is a growing regional and international market for households' consumption and industrial use.**
- ✓ **Unpredictable domestic marketing policies result in weakly organized domestic marketing systems, and uncompetitive pricing systems.**

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Objective

- i. Determine how enhanced **policy frameworks and governance mechanisms** improve the **protein self-sufficiency at the country level and provide decent livelihoods** for farmers and other agents involved in the poultry value chain.
- ii. Determine how enhanced **policy frameworks and governance mechanisms** improve the **competitiveness and sustainability** of domestic poultry meat.

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Economic analysis
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Soft systems methodology

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

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Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Various ministries and agencies are responsible for policymaking and regulation across the agriculture sector.**
 - Although the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MoFA) takes the lead, several other ministries also contribute to agriculture-related policies.
- ✓ **Ghana's trade policy and industrial agenda aim to boost agricultural competitiveness and diversification but must also support sustainable practices without compromising environmental and social standards.**
 - Ensure that agricultural development projects and policies enhance the livelihoods of local communities, including smallholder farmers and marginalized groups. This entails equitable access to resources, land, and opportunities, alongside promoting gender equality and youth participation in agriculture.
 - The Food and Agricultural Sector Development Policy (FASDEP), Medium Term Agricultural Sector Investment Plans (METASIP), and other strategic documents focus on increasing agricultural productivity, which directly impacts food availability and accessibility.
- ✓ **Agency imbalances undermine the sustainability of smaller operations, impacting livelihoods in the domestic poultry industry.**
 - Larger commercial entities have better access to markets and pricing power compared to smallholder farmers
 - Larger producers have preferential access to critical inputs (access to feed, veterinary services, financing, and technology), while smaller producers face barriers.
 - The ability of foreign producers to dominate the local market through cheaper imports creates power imbalances.
- ✓ **There is lack of communication or dissemination of government initiatives within the poultry sector, and programs are concentrated in only some geographical areas.**
 - Rearing for Food and Jobs (RFJ), which focuses on promoting poultry rearing as a means to enhance food security and job creation was recognized by 8% of the respondents.
 - The Broiler Revitalization Program, aimed to boost the broiler chicken segment of the industry, was known by 6% of the respondents.
 - Amplified Project was recognized by 2% of the poultry farmers, this project seems to facilitate linkages between farmers, feed millers, and hatcheries.
- ✓ **Research institutions and universities work with the industry to conduct research on improving poultry breeds, feed efficiency, disease management, and overall farm management practices.**
- ✓ **Ensuring that women poultry farmers have equal access to resources such as land, capital, training, and inputs (feed, chicks, vaccines) is essential for promoting gender equality in the sector.**
 - Offer gender-sensitive training and extension services that cater to the needs and schedules of women can help increase their participation and success in poultry farming.
 - Support women's participation in leadership roles within poultry associations, cooperatives, and community groups can ensure their perspectives and needs are considered in decision-making processes.
 - Facilitate women's access to markets and developing strategies to overcome barriers to market entry can help women maximize the income from their poultry activities.

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Poultry farming can contribute to nutritional wellbeing by providing a source of protein and income for purchasing diverse foods.**
 - The availability and affordability of poultry products enhances the protein intake of the population, addressing issues of malnutrition and protein-energy malnutrition.
- ✓ **With high demand for poultry products both in local and international markets, farmers who are able to efficiently produce and market their poultry products can significantly improve their incomes.**
 - The poultry sector can create employment opportunities not only for the farmers but also for others in the community, including in feed production, veterinary services, marketing, and distribution.
 - Poultry has relatively short production cycles compared to many crops or other livestock, allowing for quicker returns on investment. This can improve cash flow and income for farmers. However, the study found that farmers were barely making profits from their poultry farms
 - The poultry sector creates jobs across its value chain, from production to marketing, thus providing employment to individuals in both rural and urban areas.
 - This includes income stability, financial security, and the capacity to afford basic needs and invest in the future.
- ✓ **Poultry production is highly valued in Ghana, accounting for 14% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), indicating its substantial economic impact.**
 - Jobs in the production of poultry feed, including roles in feed mills and in the cultivation of feed ingredients like maize and soybeans are important to note.
 - Employment for veterinarians and veterinary assistants who specialize in poultry health, providing services such as disease management, vaccination programs, and health consultations.
- ✓ **Production costs of national poultry products end up being very high, thus weakening their competitiveness with imported products.**
 - Cost of most poultry feed ingredients such as soybean meal, cotton meals, maize, oyster shells, wheat brand meal, dicalcium, and fish meal continue to increase astronomically. Poultry feed is mostly imported, making farmers subject to price volatility in international markets.
 - 70% of the costs for poultry farming in Ghana are allocated to feed the birds.
 - The high production and transaction costs of domestic poultry meat in Ghana does not allow to compete with imported products (often subsidized and processed).
 - High electricity tariff is another major factor accounting for the high production cost the poultry sub-sector in Ghana. These costs are further exacerbated by the depreciating local currency against major trading currencies such as the Euro and the US Dollar.
 - While there are some consistent costs across the industry (e.g., the price of local broiler DOC), there is considerable variability in many of the costs associated with poultry farming. This could be due to geographical differences, differences in scale, or access to different suppliers or resources.
 - The price volatility in feed and transportation can greatly impact the profitability and sustainability of poultry farming operations.
- ✓ **Infrastructure for poultry and livestock production, processing and marketing remain a major challenge to the sector.**
 - Some of the large commercial farmers do have their own processing facilities but lack modern equipment.
 - It was estimated that about 58.1% of the poultry farms were in rural areas. This suggests that the majority of poultry farms have to deal with the general infrastructural challenges facing rural communities

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“The living income differential for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Objective

- i. Explore the role that **stocks and market power** have played in **price development after Living Income Differential (LID)**.
- ii. Understand why Living Income Differential Initiative did not work in its current setup in Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire by delving into the **structure of the cocoa market** and the **price-setting activities**.
- iii. Explore whether the futures market limits the **negotiation power of cocoa producing nations**.

Methods

- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

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“The living income differential (LID) for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Money flows and decision-making lack transparency and therefore weaken national policies for sustainable cocoa and international competitiveness.**
- ✓ **Lack of regulation leads to race to the bottom in taking corporate responsibility for human rights violations in the value chain.**
- ✓ **Political crisis fueled the volatility of the cocoa price in Côte d'Ivoire from 2000 onwards.**
 - Corruption is consequence of lack of transparency, high power imbalances and low access to justice or remediation.
- ✓ **Lack of coordination among coffee value chain actors leads to high volatility and periods of oversupply with consequent price drops.**
- ✓ **Power imbalances (with multinationals and intermediaries exerting pressure through future market systems) limit agents' bargaining power in price setting, especially farmers who cannot enforce a price that secure themselves a subsistence level.**
 - The design and setup of the Living Income Differential (LID) was top-down. Farmers and NGOs have no deeper knowledge of the initiative and were not included in the process.
 - The implementation of LID, governments of Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire overestimated the influence of farmers and underestimated the power of market mechanisms.
 - Power imbalances are reinforced and exacerbated by market concentration processes in some parts of the value chain (trading-grinding and chocolate companies).
- ✓ **Unequal distribution of risks and benefits leads to high poverty rates.**
 - Despite efforts to improve livelihoods in the face of instable market prices, most cocoa farming families in the leading producing countries earn less than a living income.
 - Human rights violations - such as child labour, malnutrition, low access to decent housing, health care, etc. - are mostly linked with poverty and lack of living income.
- ✓ **Farming families rely heavily on cash crops, which are typically a male-dominated source of income.**
- ✓ **Weak governance of cocoa cooperatives leads to bad protection of interests of cocoa farmers.**
- ✓ **Volatility of exchange rates of local currency against US dollar/ EUR, together with inflation rates, influence farmgate prices and represent a risk for processing local-based businesses.**
- ✓ **Harvested volumes per hectare are under pressure not only from weather and climate instability but also due to the 2021 Russian attack on Ukraine, which caused a sharp rise in fertilizer prices.**
- ✓ **Dependency of producing countries on tax revenue from exporting commodities.**
 - This dependency puts producing countries in a weak negotiating position on the cocoa market (e.g., LID was under massive pressure after implementation, with a significative reduction of country differentials).
 - It also leads to a lack of investment in the local economy.

“The living income differential (LID) for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ The key to strengthening or weakening a company's competitive position in cocoa processing is cost efficiency and vertical integration, generating additional profits downstream in the supply chain.
- ✓ Price fluctuation due to the liberalization of cocoa markets in producing countries, driven by IMF structural adjustment programs:
 - Côte d'Ivoire partially reversed its liberalization in 2012.
 - Ghana reformed its market a couple of times but never completely abolished the strong state influence on the national cocoa trade.
- ✓ Droughts, devastating forest fires, among other climate events , influence price volatility.
- ✓ There is a clear link between the decline in real cocoa prices, incomes and human rights abuses, as well as with severe ecological damage in cocoa -producing regions.
 - Child labour rates increased as farmers tried to reduce production costs by trimming their expenditure on labour relating to weeding and harvesting, to cope with prices drop.
- ✓ Modern communication technologies and transparency on the levels of stocks on cocoa products are crucial to understand the links between the levels of stocks and the price of cocoa.
- ✓ Measures to stabilize prices by supply management (e.g., Buffer stocks and export quotas).
 - Côte d'Ivoire: Measures to regulate the market, like system of advance sales of the harvest (70-80%) with the selling price based on the buyers' expectations of the future price development.
 - Ghana: Institution responsible for regulating the entire cocoa sector, with the goal of paying out of 72% of the net-FOB. The difference is used to pay costs of support activities like transportation, inputs, advisory services, etc. A minimum price is set by a committee (farmers-ministries-COCOBOD).
- ✓ Futures markets provide protection for actors with high capital reserves against price fluctuations and have no preconditions for human rights protection.
- ✓ In futures markets, the risks are reduced to differential risks - difference between the premiums and discounts around futures prices in buying and selling transactions.
 - Futures price has influence on the physical price of commodities traded on commodity futures exchanges, acting as a guide.
 - Asymmetric information plays a crucial role in traders' negotiations on differentials.
- ✓ Differentials reflect cocoa features related to quality and yield but are also result of negotiations between sellers and buyers of cocoa beans.

“The living income differential (LID) for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The introduction of the LID lead to cocoa from Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire being significantly more expensive than cocoa from other countries.**
 - With oversupply, companies did not want to buy cocoa at the price necessary to stabilize a country differential and the LID. This put a lot of pressure on the country differentials, which decreased significantly for these two countries.

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“The living income differential for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Objective

- i. Assess the effects of trade/ tax policies on the development of the local dairy sector in WA, which is crucial for the socioeconomic development of pastoral and agro-pastoral regions, food and nutrition security, and for a healthy trade balance and foreign currency reserves.

Methods

- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Modelling methods

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

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“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **EU should support changes at the WTO and EPA levels that allow West African countries to protect their dairy systems, given the region's specific challenges.**
 - An increase in the Common Exterior Tariff (CET) would put some countries in breach of their WTO commitments.
 - Raising the CET would pose specific problems for Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana, which have signed EPAs with the EU
- ✓ **The EU has not implemented policies to ban or reduce palm oil imports, despite its deforestation impact, and has indirectly encouraged replacing milk fat with palm oil.**
- ✓ **Economic and social development of rural areas is a key issue, given growing numbers of conflicts and levels of instability in the region (lower income levels and higher poverty rates).**
 - Rural areas are hit hardest since imported powder processing plants are concentrated in cities, even though rural regions, where most local milk activities occur.
- ✓ **It is essential that representatives of the local dairy sector, CSOs, and their allies in the political sphere make a substantiated and effective case to the states in the region and ECOWAS, to advocate for changes in trade governance and regulations in response to their specific conditions.**
- ✓ **In response to civil society campaigns, the EU has recognized the problem of the lack of transparency and created a specific tariff line to identify fat filled milk powders.**
 - At ECOWAS level, this multiactor approach has led to the Regional Milk Offensive.
- ✓ **The system of subsidies (CAP) is ultimately used for dumping practices, preventing West African countries to be competitive on the global market.**
 - CAP subsidies enable manufacturers to pay a lower price for milk than they would have to if there were no subsidies, and therefore to sell their output (in particular, fat filled milk powder) at a more competitive price on the global market.
- ✓ **Trade policy, in particular the ECOWAS Common External Tariff – CET, influences the price of various dairy products and derivatives imported by West African countries. Trade defense measures should be integrated into the broader framework of the ECOWAS Regional Offensive for the Promotion of Local Milk Value Chains in West Africa.**
 - The measures explored include raising CET, abolition of VAT on milk products, ban on import of fat filled milk powders, making dairy import conditional on the use of local mil, or combinations of these options.
 - This will enhance milk production capacity and support the development of the sector, particularly in collection and processing.
- ✓ **Imported milk powder is cheaper, easier to store, and more readily available than local dairy products, leading to a shift in consumer preferences towards imports, weakening demand for local milk.**

“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Proposed tax and trade policies would lead to a fall in powder imports and the increase in milk production, which would result in a significant rise in the self-sufficiency rate.**
 - Food dependency means not only a considerable import bill for the region, but it also increases the vulnerability of consumers, particularly the poorest urban consumers, as the price surges in 2007-2008 and 2022 showed.
- ✓ **Competition from powder exports is tending to weaken the growth rate of milk production in the West African region, as well as the jobs and income associated with milk production and collection.**
 - The proportion of consumption covered by regional production, is as low as 41%, compared with 60% at the beginning of the 21st century.
- ✓ **Changes in producer prices depend on increased demand for local milk, with options that boost local milk volumes leading to the greatest price and income gains for livestock farmers.**
 - Level of the ECOWAS Common External Tariff (CET) – influences the price of the various dairy products and derivatives imported by West African countries.
 - An increase in the CET with the scrapping of VAT on products made from fresh milk (18% increase in price and 29% increase in income).
 - Add a ban on imports of fat filled milk powder (21% increase in price and 33% increase in income).
 - Making the use of powders by processors made conditional on the incorporation of 20% local milk would also have a significant effect (10% increase in price and 16% increase in income).
 - The price rises are relatively modest, and a flexible CET would protect consumers in the event of a spike in global prices.
- ✓ **Formalization and further industrialization of the dairy sector, more particularly the production and processing side, risks exclusion of women who currently play a central role in the production and informal marketing of milk.**

“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Objective

- i. Identify the **flows, actors, and explore their roles** and responsibilities in respecting social sustainability in the sugarcane ethanol value chain from Brazil and Peru into Belgium.
- ii. Explore the impacts of **sugarcane ethanol value chain and EU policies** in **livelihoods, human rights,** and **the environment** in producing countries.

Methods

- Focus group discussions
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Surveys
- Text/content analysis
- Value chain mapping

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

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“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Belgian/EU energy policies increase the demand for biofuels. Due to market conditions, most come from countries where they compete with agricultural land and incur in human rights violations.**
 - The EU employs biofuels in road transport as a crucial strategy to address the climate crisis and reduce reliance on fossil fuels from contentious sources, as outlined in the Clean Energy for All Europeans package and Renewable Energy Directives (RED I-IV).
 - In 2009, EU directives mandated a 20% share of renewable energy in the EU and 10% of road transport fuels from renewable sources by 2020, later raised to 14% by 2030.
 - While the Belgian Government promotes the consumption of gasoline-bioethanol blends as a low carbon footprint solution, the local impacts of sugar-cane-based ethanol prove that this energy source is anything but sustainable.
- ✓ **Companies promising special benefits to political leaders and their communities, and pressuring them to requalify lands, buy at a cheaper price, or obtain additional water extraction permits, allowing the rapid expansion of biofuel production.**
 - Businesses that had at least one contact with a public official and that paid a bribe to a public official or were asked for a bribe by those public officials.
 - Peru: In the Chira Valley, the PECP (Special Chira–Piura Project) played a key role by portraying itself as the rightful landowner. It successfully labeled large 'unproductive' land areas as matters of 'public interest' for new ethanol investments.
 - Brazil: In 2018, Repórter Brasil uncovered that Marcos Marinho Lutz, CEO of Cosan and a Raízen Board member, was the second-largest campaign donor to Brazilian federal deputy Tereza Cristina. She led the special commission that approved a bill easing pesticide regulations, known as the "poison package."
- ✓ **The entry of biofuel agribusinesses has eroded local governance, causing a decline in communal authority during land negotiations and fostering distrust in regional and national authorities.**
 - In San Lucas de Colán, Maple Ethanol's presence led to evictions and land ownership uncertainties, reshaping the dynamics between the peasant community as a political and legal entity and its members.
 - Power imbalance between government-backed corporations and local communities has eroded local authority in land negotiations.
- ✓ **Biofuel plantations do not respect labour rights such as freedom of association and collective bargaining.**
 - Peru: Annual collective bargaining agreement (CBA) negotiations at Caña Brava and Agroaurora reflect a complex company-union dynamic, with labor rights not assured. Unions were formed in response to labor abuses like forced overtime and unfair dismissal.
 - Brazil: Moema Mill faced a lawsuit for safety failures, non-payment of commuting hours, and coercion of workers. In Piracicaba, auditors found sugarcane cutters without contracts, facing poor conditions and inadequate meals. Raízen has multiple labor lawsuits on issues like overtime, outsourcing, and work accidents.

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Biofuel production increases physical violence, including gender-based violence, either directly through the enterprise staff or through the tensions created in the community after the change of socioeconomic conditions.**
 - Peru: Some female interviewees pointed out that, since ethanol investments arrived, alcoholism and subsequent gender-based violence have been on the rise.
 - Brazil: Between 2018 and 2021, Pernambuco was accused of invasion of conservation areas, expulsion of traditional communities, pollution of mangroves, gender violence, threats, private imprisonment, and torture. In 2010 alone, 56 Guarani were reported to have been assassinated. In 2013, Guarani leader Ambrósio Vilhalva, a prominent advocate against the practices of the cane sugar industry, was murdered in his community in Mato Grosso do Sul.
- ✓ **Workers faced severe health issues due to excessive working days without breaks.**
 - Negligence contributed to safety failures, including fatal accidents.
 - Brazil: Raízen exploited a 2017 labor law reform to reduce workers' rights, discontinuing payment for commuting hours, causing up to 30% income loss.
 - Peru: Deductions significantly impact Caña Brava workers' salaries, as the company pays the statutory minimum wage (PEN 1,025 or €269), insufficient to cover living expenses. Consequently, many employees frequently work overtime. Workers follow a 4x3 workweek, with four consecutive 12-hour shifts and three days off.
- ✓ **Biofuel production increasing poverty because of reduced access to traditional livelihoods and/or promises from biofuel companies to reduce the poverty rate not accomplished.**
 - Peru: Between 2004 and 2019, the share of the population living under the national poverty line fell from 58.7 percent to only 20.2 percent. While the poverty rate declined over the period, people climbing out of poverty could not manage to reach much above the poverty line and were thus vulnerable to falling into poverty in the event of a shock.
- ✓ **Severe human rights violations and human health have been identified in producing areas:**
 - This includes harming the rights of women, children, and indigenous communities, worker's rights, civil and political rights, health rights, the right to education, food, adequate housing, physical integrity, and the right to live.
 - Peru: The social impacts of sugarcane ethanol production in the Chira Valley, Piura, Northern Peru have been widely documented by local media, human rights organizations, community-based organizations, and NGOs. The contamination of the air has led to the prevalence of chronic respiratory diseases, especially among children and the elderly. The increasing incidence of asthma amongst children affects women more severely because caring for ill family members is a task relegated exclusively to them.
 - Brazil: According to the Guarani, the sugarcane production on their lands has had detrimental impacts on their indigenous community, including health issues related to the use of chemicals on the plantation, deforestation, a loss of access to natural medicine, environmental degradation and death of fish and plants due to water pollution.

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

✓ Land grabbing by biofuel companies often involves violent actions, corruption, legal loopholes, and a lack of consultation.

- Several thousand hectares were bought at prices representing as low as 4% of the market value and without proper consultation with local populations. This led to the legal dispossession of common lands and the enclosure of human settlements and public spaces, affecting up to 40,404 inhabitants.

In Peru:

- Maple Ethanol's adjudicated lands, spanning 924ha, included settlements.
- Around 200 families in La Huaca (Peru) were affected, with homes and communal areas included without consultation. Some faced eviction, and access to important areas like the dry forest lands of El Tablazo was restricted despite their significance for local activities. (There are instances of legal dispossession of communal lands).

In Brazil:

- Sugarcane production on Guarani lands has resulted in adverse effects, including health issues from chemical use, deforestation, loss of natural medicine access, environmental degradation, and water pollution impacting fish and plants. The Guarani were not consulted due to the Brazilian government's failure to protect their land rights.
- Under the Bolsonaro administration, conflicts over their lands persist, leading to intimidation and assault by gunmen from large-scale farms.

✓ Biofuel production demanding irrigation water that is taken away from already scarce water reservoirs.

- In 2007, the Ministry of Agriculture declared water scarcity, suspending new licenses. Yet, in 2008, Maple Ethanol received a two-year water reservation extension. The Peruvian government supports Piura's ethanol industry by allowing Agroaurora and Caña Brava year-round access to Chira River's water reservoirs.

✓ These investments facilitated the arrival of international agribusinesses in the region and the capture of several natural resources fundamental for food production (land and water) with severe long-term impacts.

- After evaluation of the negative impacts of the investments the banks decided to stop the funding, but the land and water remained in the hands of the investors or sold to other agribusinesses.
- As of 2023 most of the resources have not been devolved to the communities, and the facilities have continued to produce biofuels for EU and other markets.

✓ The lack of social monitoring in EU/BE energy policies drove the expansion of biofuel plantations on land creating social conflicts.

- Since 2012, the European Commission must report every two years on the impacts of its energy policies for soil, water, and air; the affordability and availability of food, for people living in developing countries; and the respect of land use and labor rights.
- The national Belgian transposition of REDII included a new set of specific monitoring criteria. The DG Environment will carry out for the first time in 2024, an evaluation of the sustainability aspects of the implementation of the provisions of this law.

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The surging demand for biofuels significantly impacts the prices of cane sugar and its derivatives, affecting food commodities and food security.**
 - Between January 2005 and June 2008, maize prices nearly tripled, palm oil prices increased by 200%, and soybean prices by 192%, driven by an unusual joint movement in agricultural products.
 - In a country like Guatemala, they are insufficient to feed a family: in this country, the EU's second-largest supplier of ethanol, malnutrition affects 1 out of 2 children and 80% of the indigenous population, which provides the labor for large plantations.
- ✓ **Peru exploited the removal of import duties on ethanol, increasing exports to the EU and substituting them with cheap imports from the US.**
 - Lifting import duties increasing biofuel imports from Peru into EU.
- ✓ **Belgium imports from other countries because of cheaper biofuel production and international market dynamics.**
 - Brazil was the key origin for sugarcane feedstock, accounting for 73% of the sugarcane-based bioethanol consumed on the Belgium market in 2021.
 - EU has become a prominent market for Peruvian ethanol, with 94% of Peruvian exports going to European Union markets today
 - Belgium predominantly uses imported first-generation biofuels from food and feed crops, leading to substantial global social and environmental impacts.
- ✓ **The lack of transparency in these supply chains hinders tracking physical flows and identifying stakeholders.**
 - Companies have limited obligations for public disclosure, and some can request confidentiality. The bioethanol market's volatility leads to shifts in sourcing countries, complicating traceability.
 - Transparency issues make it difficult to trace ethanol from Brazil and Peru to Dutch facilities or identify responsible actors. Connections with customers in Belgium are unclear, as companies and authorities do not disclose information on relationships and feedstock flows.
- ✓ **Belgium deemed biofuels 'sustainable' and introduced fiscal incentives in 2006. Gasoline with ≥7% bioethanol enjoyed tax reductions.** However, the criteria for environmental and social responsibility were deemed insufficient.
 - In 2003, the EU set biofuel targets of 2% by end-2005 and 5.75% by end-2010.
 - To comply, Belgium enacted laws from 2011 to 2015, increasing biofuel incentives and setting a minimum blending target. These changes boosted demand in the EU for bioethanol derived from food crops, such as cereals and sugar, and facilitated global investments in biofuel production.
- ✓ **Loans from development banks drove the expansion of biofuels in non-EU countries** often without the necessary checkups of socioeconomic and environmental safeguards.
 - Financial institutions like the World Bank Group, IDB and CAF began funding projects for the growing European biofuels market.
 - Belgium and the Netherlands, through their development banks BIO and FMO, invested in Maple Ethanol's operation in northern Peru.

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Objective

- i. Provide insights in the **barriers and conditions for human rights due diligence (HREDD)** to be a participatory and empowering tool to map and address **human rights risks**.
- ii. To increase insights into the **current salient human rights risks and measures** to address them in the Ugandan coffee value chain.

Methods

- Focus group discussions
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Participatory workshop

Stakeholders' engagement

- Data collection & analysis
- Exploration of linkages
- Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

- Policy and governance
- Social capital
- Human capital
- Economy and markets
- Environmental capital

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **EU coffee importers are increasingly applying HREDD, impacting business and political decisions throughout the value chain.**
 - This can, in the long term, be an incentive for national or local governments to develop and enforce better legal frameworks.
 - Governance structure in business and their HREDD can either address or strengthen power imbalances.
- ✓ **Governance structures can either address or strengthen power imbalances, as they have the potential to give right holders a lever to influence the decisions and business models along their value chain.**
 - When stakeholders are strongly engaged in identifying risks, causes, and solutions, this gives them a lever to influence decisions and business models.
- ✓ **National regulations that protect or harm human rights (equity, non-discrimination) need to be considered in HREDD processes, as will influence the label of certain locations as risky and the decisions of companies to work there.**
- ✓ **Application of HREDD on health and safety standards are an important measure against which salient risks and future actions to address risks are determined.**
 - When HREDD provides indication that safe pest management, access to toilets or access to drinking water are at stake, it will lead to a prioritization and actions to address these risks.
- ✓ **Land availability, productivity, and crop diversification directly impact the food security of small-scale producers.**
- ✓ **Lack of living income for farmers or lack of living wage for workers, is one of the key root causes for child labour during production.**
 - Parents are aware that child labour can harm the health and schooling of their children and would avoid child labour if they had that possibility. However, due to poverty they can not afford missing/replacing this extra human resource, as that would interfere with other basic needs such as food.
- ✓ **Food insecurity is strongly linked to poverty and lack of living income/wage and their root causes.**
- ✓ **Poverty limits small-scale farmers' ability to plan long-term and invest in productivity, resilience, or sustainable production methods.**
- ✓ **Most activities linked to coffee production are carried out under inadequate working conditions, preventing farmers and agricultural workers from accessing health services, while at the same time posing risks to their health (insect bites, falling from trees, exhaustion).**
 - Informality of labour also means no contributions to social security/health schemes are paid.
 - Lack of living income and living wages also limit the farmers' and workers' possibility to health services when they need it.

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Social norms are a cause for the very limited land ownership by women and the limited involvement of women in coffee sale.**
 - The case study showed that increased involvement of women had a positive effect on the productivity and the quality.
- ✓ **Collaboration between stakeholders** enables more systemic solutions.
 - Collaboration between stakeholders, in this case between the coffee farmers, the primary and secondary cooperatives and the coffee buyer/exporter plays an important role in identifying risks and attempts to address them.
- ✓ **Child labour has become a taboo topic and may be more and more underreported in cases where sustainability standards use a binary pass/fail approach.**
 - There is a risk of concealing the problem rather than addressing it.
- ✓ **There are no trade unions in the coffee sector in this region and most labour relationships are compromised by informality. As a result, farmers and farm workers are unable to collectively bargain, have less access to grievance mechanisms, and less leverage on their working conditions.**
- ✓ **Consumption volumes, purchasing practices and prices applied by the coffee buyer, and price setting practices/transparency applied by the primary and secondary coffee cooperative all influence the farm gate prices and hence the farmers income and resilience**
 - On production side, plot surface, productivity, diversification, and safety issues (e.g. theft of harvest) also influence farmer's income and (lack of) poverty.
- ✓ **Productivity is determined in part by land availability, but also by production methods and crop substance methods.**
 - Intercropping and shade cropping, as well as agronomy training contributed to production quality and quantity.
 - Registration of women farmers and increased involvement and recognition of women in the coffee production also did.
- ✓ **Volumes of consumption of the Fairtrade coffee in Belgium determine the share of production that the cooperative in Uganda can sell at the better Fairtrade conditions.**
 - It influences the Belgian retailer's ability to adjust prices and support farmers.
- ✓ **Middlemen, while providing credit and logistics in the coffee value chain, exploit power imbalances by offering little transparency on quality or pricing and often adulterate coffee to maximize profits.**
 - These middlemen sell their untraceable coffee to domestic or international exporters.

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

Objective

- i. Investigate the impact that **labour conditions and costs** have on the **competitiveness of beef's** international trade.
- ii. Investigate the **role of environmental component** in the international trade of beef commodities.

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Economic analysis
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **National and international legislation may limit production when excessive amounts of nutrients and emissions are produced.**
 - Emerging dynamics would reduce demand (if sustainability is not addressed) or increase demand, including for export (if sustainability concerns are addressed).
- ✓ **Lobby groups, animal welfare legislation, and consumer attention could trigger efforts towards labelling of the sustainability of beef, stimulating exports, and beef demand.**
 - This intervention would generate positive returns for investments in improved sustainability.
- ✓ **Importation of beef commodities can help the less competitive country to nourish its population at reasonable price.**
- ✓ **Consumers preferences may shift production to low emissions and animal welfare certified products.**
- ✓ **Low prices of imported beef commodities will discourage local production, limiting the number of farms and cows, revenues and profitability, hence leading to a reduction of employment in the beef primary production.**
- ✓ **Access to capital influences technology adoption, which reduces labour intensity, and reducing nutrient concentration and GHG emissions.**
 - Capital influences technology adoption allows to reduce the cost of production and increase cost competitiveness, resulting in the further growth of farm size.
 - Labour costs are pushed higher by the increasing number of employees and by the increased skills.
- ✓ **Higher beef production results in higher land requirements, feed production, which may face higher costs if land availability is constrained.**
- ✓ **Higher beef production results in higher manure generation, causing an increase in nutrient concentration per hectare and higher GHG emissions.** (The export and import of beef will generate CO2 emissions related to transport).
- ✓ **By increasing the size of exploitations, their competitiveness is strengthened due to lower unitary costs.**

“Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Objective

- i. Evaluate the impact that **GLOBAL G.A.P. certification** has on access to international and regional markets with respect to **social sustainability**.
- ii. Analyze how **market access** has enabled farmers to produce high-quality and sustainable products and reach **higher prices in regional and international markets?**
- iii. Analyze the impact of **certification** on broader socio-economic considerations (**labour conditions, discrimination, gender and human rights, and market and power imbalances**).
- iv. Analyze how market access has enabled **farmers to produce high-quality and sustainable products and reach higher prices in regional and international markets?**

Methods

- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Surveys

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Some regulations and government policies, such as high taxation, pose high transactions costs and have thereby hindered the sector from achieving its full potential.**
- ✓ **EU regulations on deforestation would affect practices on avocado and mango farms that have been clearing forest areas to plant these fruit trees for the past 3 years.**
 - About 30% of avocado farmers have uprooted other crops
- ✓ **Working conditions within mango and avocado value chains are strongly influenced by the type of society in which it is contextualized.**
 - Concerning the prevention or compensation activities affecting the health and safety conditions in the workplace, Kenya leaves the decision of the management of the harmful works to the relation between employee and employer.
- ✓ **Health and social welfare are addressed in different ways along the value chains of Mango and Avocado.**
 - They are strongly influenced by the working conditions and rights concerning e.g. to minimum age for retirement, prevention and compensation activities, leaves, overtime remuneration, etc.
- ✓ **Working conditions along the value chain are strongly linked to gender inequality and associated imbalances.**
 - Many women are discouraged from taking leave and returning to work by employer practices that affect their employment security, remuneration and career path, as many men are not encouraged to take the leave to which they are entitled.
- ✓ **Labour contracts and grievance mechanisms are not commonly used among avocado and mango farmers.**
 - Working hours vary widely depending on the type of contract, being relevant to the risk of accidents and the occurrence of work-related illnesses.
 - Working conditions include welfare conditions such as life insurance and health care.
- ✓ **A generally acknowledged merit of certification is that it addresses and attempts to solve gender inequality and associated imbalances, having a positive impact on farm worker’s health and financial benefits.**
- ✓ **Certification increased crop yields in most cases and sometimes even reduced the number of working hours.**

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ Certification documents make it possible to obtain higher prices and increase farmers' incomes by improving their access to markets with better prices.
 - It also helps to improve working conditions that affect remuneration.
- ✓ Certification increased farmers' access to bank credits.
- ✓ Certification enhance farmers' risk mitigation and business management, increasing their resilience.
- ✓ Certification facilitates avocado and mango farmers to access state aid and increase the ability of farmers to bargain for better prices with buyers.
 - Certification helps enhancing the trust between farmers and buyers, who in some cases require certification documents to do a transaction.
- ✓ Inadequate storage and transportation facilities prevent avocado and mango industry to be competitive.

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Objective

- i. Assess the **effectiveness of ethical trade** initiatives in improving **labour conditions** and **human rights** in the South African wine sector.

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Fieldwork/ on-farm visits
- Key informants' interviews
- Text/content analysis
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Surveys

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Local socio-economic legislation governs the transformation of ownership (Black Economic Empowerment) and land reform within the South African wine sector.**
- ✓ **The existing housing policy for farm workers is outdated and inadequate and does not address the needs of seasonal and off-farm workers.**
 - Many rural towns have become overcrowded and underserved as a result of the influx of off-farm workers.
- ✓ **Local labour legislation governs the minimum working conditions and remuneration for workers on South African wine farms.**
 - Farm worker wages, set at R 25.42 (€ 1.28) per hour in 2023, are widely considered inadequate for sustaining a decent standard of living. Many struggle to support their families on this income, as it falls short of a living wage in the Western Cape province, leaving workers unable to cover their basic needs.
 - Wine grape production in South Africa is one of the most labour-intensive sub-sectors in agriculture.
- ✓ **Unemployment levels in the wine producing regions are lower than compared to national levels, which contributes to the challenge of sustaining the livelihoods of a significant part of the population.**
 - Poverty levels in these areas are still high and persistent.
 - The strong link between unemployment and poverty is evident, with nearly 31 % of the population living below the food poverty line in 2022.
 - The unemployment rate in South Africa has increased steadily from 25 % in 2012 to 34 % in 2022. Rural areas face even higher unemployment rates, as reported by the Human Research Council in 2020.
- ✓ **There are low levels of unionization and collective bargaining power among workers, leading to challenges in enforcing their rights and accessing legal assistance.**
 - In the agricultural sector, producers and workers show signs of agency and dialogue.
 - Some producers adopt progressive labor practices and engage in ethical trade, while workers form associations, participate in protests, and negotiate.
- ✓ **The low level of trust between employers and employees is underpinned by poor professional management and talent retention as well as high levels of inequality, unemployment, and poverty.**
- ✓ **In South Africa's agricultural sector, spatial inequality is marked by a developed white commercial sector and a black small-scale sector centered on subsistence farming.**
- ✓ **Dismissal consequences are more severe in rural areas, where workers may lose their homes and have limited alternative work and housing options.**
 - The right of fair dismissal is limited or non-existent for seasonal workers, who rely on reemployment the next season.

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Migrant women earn below the legal minimum wage, with many lacking contracts, social security, and unemployment.**
 - Women endure exposure to pesticides, inadequate facilities, and unrealistic harvest targets, leading to long, uninterrupted work hours and resulting in health issues and injuries.
 - Migrant women also face racism, sexism, and xenophobia from farm stakeholders, along with instances of sexual exploitation, harassment, and abuse in their pursuit of employment.
- ✓ **Wine sector necessitates sufficient training and education for farm workers.**
 - This aligns with a noticeable disparity, where a diminishing core of wellskilled permanent workers enjoys better conditions, while a rising number of seasonal workers with lower skills and limited training face poorer employment terms.
- ✓ **Compliance with social standards in the South African wine sector may require the provision of social services to farm workers (e.g. housing, clean water, childcare, maternity leave, school, healthcare)**
- ✓ **Compliance with social standards in the South African wine sector require adequate occupational healthcare for farm workers, and equal labour conditions and remuneration for women farm workers.**
- ✓ **Compliance with social standards in the South African wine sector may require the development of local communities (e.g. rights of tenure, community engagement / community development programmes / interventions)**
- ✓ **Wine consumption in the EU market is relatively stagnant, which has put downward pressure on South African wine production and exports and has had a negative impact on employment.**
- ✓ **South Africa faces a relative high number of Non -Tariff Measures (NTM's) when exporting wine to the EU.**
 - South Africa has preferential tariffs for its wine exports to the EU due to concessions stipulated in the SADGEPA agreement.
- ✓ **Over the years, the wine sector has increasingly focused on exporting bulk wine rather than bottled wine, which has negatively affected local value addition within the industry .**
 - Over half of South Africa's wine production is exported.
 - Bulk wine exports have exceeded bottled wine exports since 2011, with the value of bulk wine exports rising from 26% in 2008 to 36% by 2022.

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **South Africa ranks sixth in terms of the quality margin of its wine; lower than its “new world” counterparts.**
 - This is in line with the marketing strategy of South African wine as “good value for money”.
- ✓ **The profitability of the South African wine sector is under pressure.**
 - Data from Vinpro (2021) shows that since 2015 the growth in production cost has outweighed the increase in the producer price.
 - For a large proportion of wine exports (the out-of-quota quantity), South Africa faced a higher MFN tariff. This puts pressure on the profitability and competitiveness of South African wine.

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

"Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets"

Objective

- i. Understand the **role of local legislation** in strengthening **dairy product competitiveness**.
- ii. Investigate the impact that **labour conditions** and costs have on the **competitiveness** of dairy products on international trade.
- iii. Explore how the **environment** may impact the **farm competitiveness** and trade of **dairy commodities**.

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Economic analysis
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ Many women are discouraged from taking leave and returning to work by employer practices that affect their employment security, remuneration and career path, as many men are not encouraged to take the leave to which they are entitled.
- ✓ In Brazil most of the workers do not have an employment contract, so they cannot access to social services, insurance, nor guaranteed medical care.
- ✓ Import of dairy commodities can help less competitive countries to nourish its population at reasonable price.
- ✓ The import of dairy commodities to less competitive countries will lead to a reduction of employment (or negatively impact working conditions) in the dairy primary productions.
- ✓ Increasing export demand of dairy products supports the local production. The market prices will guarantee revenues and profitability leading to a stable/increasing production with consequent increasing employment in dairy farms.
- ✓ The import of dairy products will decrease manure production and nutrient concentration per hectare and a reduction in local CO2 emission.
 - The export and import of dairy commodities will generate CO2 emissions related to transport.
- ✓ Increasing production would require a higher number of cows, possible with higher productivity, and consequently more land is required to produce feed for livestock or for pasture.
- ✓ When import and export of dairy products are balanced, market prices will guarantee revenues able to meet production costs level.
 - In 2022 milk price was able to cover completely the total cost of production only in South Africa, Argentina and some farms in Brazil. Even farmers supported by public subsidies (in all EU countries, some states in USA and Algeria) didn't cover the total cost of production, making some countries more competitive than others.

“Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soybean-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Objective

- i. Explore how **trade regimes** can be used as an instrument to influence land-use and food systems pathways of the soybean-meat complex in the Matopiba region of Brazil. In terms of **power inequalities** within food systems, **land grabbing, water grabbing, land-use changes** and displacement of smallholders, **deforestation and biodiversity loss** in environmentally sensitive areas.

Methods

- Causal loop diagram
- Fieldwork/ on-farm visits
- Key informants' interviews
- Secondary data review and analysis
- Participatory workshop

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The institutional and physical infrastructure contributed to the transition to prioritize the potentially most profitable crop: soybeans.**
- ✓ **The Forestry Code (Law 12.651/2012) is a federal law in Brazil that governs land use.** It designates Permanent Protection Areas (APPs) and Legal Reserves (LGs) for natural protection or sustainable resource use.
 - This allows farms in Matopiba to potentially use a significant portion, up to 80%, for crop production.
 - The Forestry Code stipulates that land conversion necessitates pre-approval (Authorization of Native Vegetation Conversion - ASVs) from relevant authorities.
 - The observed deforestation in Matopiba is illegal, which means that does not comply with the legal provision required for land use conversion according to the Forestry Code (FC).
- ✓ There is widespread evidence that the **Authorization of Native Vegetation Conversion is not transparent, accountability is weak, and enforcement of legislation is in many cases virtually non-existent**, which explains the **general illegality of deforestation**.
 - In a context of widespread impunity and weak governance in the region, any effort to increase production, even in more "sustainable intensification" forms, benefits farmers. This, in turn, gives them more resources to continue expanding crop areas over native vegetation.
 - The rate of Cerrado loss increased three times faster from 2000-2015 than in the previous 15 years.
- ✓ **The existing governance structures lack inclusivity and exhibit highly unequal power distribution among actors.**
 - The soy model in the region disproportionately benefits a privileged few non-residents, concentrating wealth in a few regional hubs and offering minimal job opportunities for the lower strata of society.
- ✓ **Local leaders report corrupting authorities like notaries and judges to validate fake land titles.**
- ✓ **There has been no government action to facilitate family farmers land regularization, and little formal support to protect their land rights.**
 - Very few small family farmers and traditional communities have documentation of their land holdings.
 - Few have old land titles that offer weak protection against expropriation and land-grabbing strategies.
- ✓ **The Soy Moratorium agreement** has been credited as an effective tool that contributed to **significant reductions in the deforestation rate of the Amazon** in the period of mid-2000s to mid-2010s, but many have pointed to its “leaking” effect to the Cerrado.
- ✓ **Large power imbalances between well-resourced, politically connected farmers, and poor, isolated family farmers leave little room for fair negotiations.**

CS14

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ Local development dynamics are associated with the size of municipalities.
 - Larger ones tend to serve as service hubs to the industry, while smaller ones as only agricultural production areas with less possibilities to trickle down and distribute resources.
 - Rural communities' express frustration that progress has not reached their margins. Instead of challenging the entire model, some propose a solution through a more equitable distribution of soy's benefits across a broader spectrum of society.
- ✓ There are multi-actor territorial agreements that encompass targets on social inclusion, sustainable production, natural resource conservation, etc., and jointly design and implement project for achieving the agreed objectives.
- ✓ The expansion of the soy-meat complex in Matopiba is inserted within the broad context of the internal migration of farmers from South Brazil and the adaptation of that crop to tropical climates and more fragile and less fertile soils that dominate Central Brazil.
- ✓ The current model of the soybean-meat expansion, which focuses on intensification, tends to increase capital accumulation, not only concentrating resources but also further facilitating more investment based on land conversion and deforestation.
 - The narrative of progress by expanding and industrializing agriculture is a mantra for some actors deeply involved within soybean-meat value chains.
- ✓ Land conflicts and violence in rural areas are serious issues in Matopiba.
 - Land grabbing is one strategy for land appropriation, operated by powerful actors to evict traditional communities of their lands. This problem has substantially accelerated in the past two decades in parallel to the soy boom.
- ✓ The expansion of soy-meat production in the Matopiba region is driven by the feed world's appetite for meat in developing and developed countries.
 - Demand for sustainably-sourced goods is increasing, but only in specific markets and in a very limited extent compared to the total market size
- ✓ Current soy-meat complex system pathway has been highly contested due to its profound impacts on local water resources, biodiversity, and carbon stocks, by fostering land conflicts, and for being associated with land and green grabbing, water grabbing severely affecting the livelihoods of family farming communities.
 - Different agricultural dynamics, including land grabbing and land disputes, makes a target of zero deforestation very challenging.

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Land conversion rates in the Matopiba region from 2000 to 2015 was primarily fueled by surging demand from export markets, especially China.**
 - China, as the world's largest importer and the primary destination for Brazilian exports, decisions made by China can significantly impact producers in Brazil.
 - Over 70% of all soybeans produced in Brazil are destined for international markets, highlighting the significant importance and dependency of the soybean-meat complex on exports.
- ✓ **The concentrated expansion of the soy-meat complex, while generating jobs, diminishes food diversity.**
- ✓ **FAPCEN (Fundação de Apoio à Pesquisa do Corredor de Exportação Norte), support research in tropical varieties of soy and became increasingly involved with the development of responsible soy production in Matopiba.**
 - FAPCEN advocates for environmental concerns, emphasizing zero deforestation and regenerative agriculture transitions.
- ✓ **There is a call for stronger efforts in understanding what alternative food systems and transition should look like, including which financial incentives could support transitions.**
- ✓ **Despite the growing demand for soybeans in the international market, stakeholders warn there is no empty land anymore, in the sense that land prices are picking up.**
- ✓ **Environmental groups advocate for traceability-focused certifications.**
 - Blending certified and non-certified soy in the value chain obstructs accurate soy origin tracing, making it nearly impossible to identify deforestation-free shipments.
 - Each soy shipment from risk areas carries potential contamination, and existing methodologies can only estimate, not guarantee, deforestation-free products.
- ✓ **In Brazil, China supports initiatives for sustainable production through dialogues with various stakeholders.**
 - President Xi Jinping promotes "ecological civilization" for sustainable development rooted in Chinese principles.

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Objective

- i. Analyze the **social** and economic impacts (**food insecurity, poverty** and **sustainable development**) of the potato trade between Egypt and Europe by increasing transparency on the costs of production, the role of different market actors and the distribution of power.

Methods

- Fieldwork/ on-farm visits
- Key informants' interviews
- Surveys
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Data collection & analysis

Exploration of linkages

Impact pathways & policy recommendations

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

Policy and governance

Social capital

Human capital

Economy and markets

Environmental capital

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The agricultural sector is composed of two systems:** the "old lands", which rely on small-scale agriculture due to **land and property fragmentation**, and the "new lands", consisting of **large export-oriented farms controlled by agricultural investment companies**.
- ✓ **The Egyptian government's agricultural and food policies follow a neoliberal model marked by inconsistencies and disconnections, prioritizing profits and short-term solutions.**
 - Since the 1980s, Egypt's agricultural policy has shifted towards market liberalization, diminishing the government's role and departing from earlier regulations on crop prices and rotation.
 - The policy orientation promotes an agricultural production pattern that is highly dependent on imported inputs, forcing farmers to depend on large agricultural companies for essential inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and pest and disease control products.
- ✓ **The government promotes large-scale agriculture through the reclamation of desert land, facilitating agricultural investors' access to large areas and to water resources.**
 - It further supports this initiative by granting permits to international companies engaged in export-oriented agriculture.
- ✓ **The UPOV Convention formally restricts farmers from producing and reproducing the seeds they cultivate, constraining the Egyptian government's capacity to breed plants or transfer technology.**
 - This compels national breeders and local seed companies to procure seeds from foreign companies.
- ✓ **Lack of participation of farmers in discussions and potential impacts on their livelihoods may not be adequately considered.**
- ✓ **Small farmers often lack bargaining power, which puts traders or middlemen in a dominant position with control over prices and putting pressure on farmers to sell.**
- ✓ **Farmers face substantial challenges in maintaining their livelihoods, exacerbated by the current economic crisis, which has pushed the poverty rate to nearly 30% in 2020.**
 - As per national poverty indicators, employed in agriculture and living in rural areas experience some of the highest poverty rates.
- ✓ **Amid the Covid-19 pandemic, the decline in potato exports, mainly directed to restaurants and processing plants in Europe, disproportionately impacted small farmers, who heavily depend on selling their crops to wholesalers serving large exporters.**
- ✓ **Child labor is prevalent in agriculture and related sectors and children are exposed to potentially fatal accidents, harassment, and abuse.**
 - In Egypt, 1.6–2 million children work, in clear violation of the law.

CS15a

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Fieldwork shows widespread unpaid family and relative labor, especially during intensive activities like planting or harvesting.**
 - Potato cultivation exhibits two contrasting patterns based on family size and the scale of available remittances. Some can hire workers, while others engage in reciprocal labor exchanges, a form of solidarity beyond economic considerations.
- ✓ **Climate change poses a significant threat to agriculture, especially small-scale farming in Egypt and throughout the North African region.**
 - Increasing droughts and high temperatures between 1998 and 2011 have served to accelerate the rate of desertification and soil degradation, triggering a series of local and regional water crises.
- ✓ **Egypt faces a water crisis. To address the challenges related to water scarcity and population growth, the government is pursuing large-scale projects focused on seawater desalination, sewage treatment, and the reuse of agricultural water.**
- ✓ **Middlemen, traders, and those able to store the crop in refrigerators for over three months benefit the most from the added value and profitability.**
 - Limited potato storage capacity poses a challenge, particularly for small farmers who, lacking the means for prolonged storage, are compelled to opt for wholesale transactions.
 - The seed import market is monopolized by 40 licensed companies.
 - Concentrated ownership of storage space raises costs for consumers, leading to higher urban potato prices.
- ✓ **Since early 2022, rising input prices due to currency liberalization have significantly increased farmers' production costs, impacting their livelihoods.**
- ✓ **Despite potatoes being a less profitable crop, farmers cultivate them for their easy to sell, helping them repay debts, purchase animals for breeding or cover other major expenses.**
- ✓ **The agriculture-for-export strategy involves the implementation of financial incentives and the establishment of close collaborations between agribusiness entities, large agri-food traders, and government agencies.**
- ✓ **Since the 1900s, the government has reduced subsidies for fertilizers and inputs, favoring an export-oriented economy.**
 - Subsidies for production inputs and credit support were withdrawn, while export subsidies provide cash support for exports and affordable production inputs for large farms.

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **Agricultural trade policies have integrated small producers into the global market without providing a competitive advantage.**
 - The government neither establishes minimum prices for crops sold by small farmers nor offers subsidies when prices fall below the cost of production, which occurs frequently.
- ✓ **Rising kerosene and diesel prices impact plowing, irrigation costs and farmers' overall profit margins.**
 - In rural areas, kerosene prices have tripled since 2014, from EGP 1.8 reaching nearly EGP 6.5 in 2023, with additional delivery costs further inflating prices.

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Objective

- i. Examine agri-food trade flows between the EU and Tunisia amidst multiple crises, including disruptions due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the influence of climate change on agriculture, and the geopolitical crisis from the Russia-Ukraine war.

Methods

- Fieldwork/ on-farm visits
- Key informants' interviews
- Surveys
- Secondary data review and analysis

Stakeholders' engagement

Analysis of agri-food trade from a systems perspective

- Policy and governance
- Social capital
- Human capital
- Economy and markets
- Environmental capital

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ **The Structural Adjustment Program aimed to reshape agricultural policies** by increasing the influence of the global market. This led to the removal of subsidies on various production units, the liberalization of prices for most agricultural products, the government withdrawal from directly managing several enterprises, and the discontinuation of support projects for many small and medium-sized farmers.
- ✓ Domestic agricultural production faces challenges compounded by the **abandonment of state support and development programs for small and medium -sized farmers.**
 - The state irrigation program’s incentives rewarded larger farmers and investment companies.
 - The government ceased supporting bank loans for small and medium-sized farmers.
- ✓ **Tunisia government implemented an irrigation program for groves** to support olive oil exports.
 - The program raised Tunisia’s irrigated land from 3% in 2010 to 20% in 2020.
- ✓ **The government transferred the support, extension, and technical assistance programs to the private sector, leaving the small-scale farmers without crucial services.**
 - Small-scale farmers are particularly affected, as they cannot afford expensive private advisors and service providers.
- ✓ **Tunisia agriculture is characterized by an unequal distribution of land, with high proportion of small and medium -scale farms.**
 - 3% are large farmers owning 34% of agricultural land, while 75% are small farmers sharing about 25% of land.
- ✓ **Women’s ownership of land is severely limited by inheritance laws and traditions that benefit men.**
 - While small farms account for nearly 80% of agricultural production, only 6.7% are run by women, who only own 5.6% of the land.
- ✓ **The wages of women working in agriculture are generally lower than those of men. In addition, they face limited access to training and extension programs and are underrepresented in professional and union structures.**
 - Only 33% of women working in the agricultural sector have social security coverage.
- ✓ Despite the importance of small -scale farmers for olive oil production, **they have to compete with large monoculture olive farms.**
 - Large monoculture olive farms occupy more than 60% of the total olive growing area.

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ Export-oriented production has led to an increase in the cost of olive oil locally, thus becoming unaffordable for Tunisians.
- ✓ Tunisia has seen a decline in average per-person consumption from 8.2 kg to 3.7 kg of olive oil in 2000 - the lowest of the Mediterranean region – which led to dietary changes that deteriorate population’s health.
- ✓ Farmers and agricultural workers are the poorest occupational groups, with poverty rates of 22.8% and 31.9% respectively.
- ✓ The shifts in the distribution of cultivated land in early 2000s resulted in approximately 40% of olive trees being planted on unsustainable or marginal land, which translated in the lowest olive farms productivity globally.
- ✓ About 80% of olive production relies on monocultures, causing soil degradation, reduced fertility, and the rapid spread of plant diseases.
- ✓ The intensive production of olive oil will lead to the further depletion of water resources in Tunisia, increasing pressure on aquifers with the associated risks of overexploitation.
 - According to a study by the Tunisian Observatory of the Economy, the production of one liter of olive oil under irrigation requires about 2,331 liters of water.
- ✓ The negotiation process of the EU-Tunisia Agreement is criticized for insufficient outreach to key groups likely to be affected (small-scale farmers, entrepreneurs, traders, consumers, and users of public services).
- ✓ The EU-Tunisia Association Agreement aims to reduce trade barriers and include provisions favoring foreign direct investment.
 - The still to be concluded EU-Tunisia Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement (DCFTAs) is part of the EU’s “new generation” trade agreements to appear to continue along this trade policy path.
- ✓ Critics express concerns about the potential exploitation of Tunisian workers and adverse effects on small and medium enterprises due to increased competition from the EU.
- ✓ Under the EU-Tunisia Association Agreement, olive oil is predominantly exported in crude form and at low cost (\$2.845 per liter in 2019) to Italy and Spain, where it is packaged and sold at higher prices.

CS15b

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Analysis of agricultural trade from a systems perspective

- ✓ The policy of export subsidies in detriment of essential needs has increased dependence on imports, especially of cereals.
 - This is taking place in the context of instability and rampant speculation driven by monopolies increasingly linked to financial markets.
- ✓ Tunisia reliance on global markets to supplement domestic demand for vegetable oils – funded by olive oil exports – increases vulnerability during food crises.
 - 20% of olive oil is for local consumption and 80% for export.
- ✓ Banks are reluctant to extend finance to small-scale farmers, who often cannot provide collateral and have difficulties navigating complex banking producers. On the other hand, microfinance institutions impose unaffordable interest rates on farmers.

CS15b

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Key linkages between agri-food trade and its embedding context, under a sustainability and human well-being perspective

Aggregate insights of case studies sharing problematic or geographical locations to explore linkages between agricultural trade and sustainability dimensions.

Below we describe the results of the analysis of elements and linkages addressed by MATS case studies according to the objective or issue tackled.

CS focused on "Governance and trade regimes for sustainable development and human rights."

As shown in Figure 9, the three most frequent driver categories among case studies focused on "Governance and trade regimes for sustainable development and human rights" are Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), Governance & political environment (PG4), and Sustainable Policies & Regulations (PG2). On the other hand, the three most frequent impacts are Income & Livelihood (H1), Resource quality & availability (EN1), and Human rights & wellbeing (H4).

FIGURE 9. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING "OBJECTIVE 1"

Appendix B can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Standards & agreements” heavily influence production and trade activities. On the other hand, “Government support & expenditure” is heavily impacted by production activities.

In the Human dimension, “Income & Livelihood” heavily influence production activities.

In the Social dimension, “Social & gender inequalities” heavily influence trade activities and are heavily impacted by production activities; furthermore, “Land tenure/ ownership rights” heavily influence and are impacted by production activities. On the other hand, “Social crises” are heavily impacted by processing activities.

In the Environmental dimension, “Resource quality & availability” heavily impacts production activities. On the other hand, “Resource efficiency” is heavily impacted by trade and consumption activities.

Finally, in the Economy & Market dimension, “Quality standards & competitiveness” heavily impact consumption activities. On the other hand, “Trade systems & market dynamics” are heavily impacted by production and trade activities.

CS focused on "Social and Human Rights Considerations for Sustainable Agricultural Trade."

As shown in Figure 10, the three most frequent driver categories are Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), Sustainable policies & regulations (PG2), and Community well-being & collaboration (S1). Similarly, the three most frequent impacts are Labor & employment (S3), Farm economics & resilience (EM4), and Community well-being & collaboration (S1).

FIGURE 10. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING "OBJECTIVE 2"

Appendix C can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Sustainable policies & regulations” heavily influence production activities.

In the Human dimension, “Food security & nutrition” heavily influence production activities and are heavily impacted by consumption activities. On the other hand, “Human rights & well-being” are heavily impacted by production activities.

In the Social dimension, “Social & gender inequalities” and “Societal awareness & measurement” heavily influence trade activities. On the other hand, “Labour & employment” heavily influence and are impacted by production activities.

In the Environmental dimension, “Resource efficiency” heavily influence production activities. On the other hand, “Resource quality & availability” and “Climate” are heavily impacted by production activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, “Trade systems & market dynamics” and “Support services & measures” are heavily impacted by production activities; furthermore, “Farm economics & resilience” are heavily impacted by production and processing activities. On the other hand, “Quality standards & competitiveness” influence production activities and are heavily impacted by trade activities.

CS focused on "Power Imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths."

As shown in Figure 11, the three most frequent driver categories are Governance & political environment (PG4), Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), and Community well-being & collaboration (S1). Similarly, the three most frequent impacts are Labor & employment (S3), Income & livelihood (H1), and Resource quality & availability.

FIGURE 11. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING "OBJECTIVE 3"

Appendix D can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Sustainable policies & regulations” heavily influence processing activities. On the other hand, “Standards & agreements” heavily influence production and trade activities.

In the human dimension, “Food security & nutrition” heavily influences consumption activities.

In the Social dimension, “Demographics” heavily influence production activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, “Macroeconomic factors” heavily influence processing activities; furthermore, “Support services & measures” are heavily impacted by production activities. On the other hand, “Quality standards & competitiveness” heavily influence trade activities and are heavily impacted by processing activities.

Below we describe the results of the analysis of elements addressed by MATS case studies according to their geographical location.

CS located in Europe and Northern America.

Within the group of CS located in the UN SDG region “Europe and Northern America” (Fig. 12), the most striking elements are, in terms of the three most frequent driver categories, Labor & Employment (S3), Income & Livelihood (H1), and Resource quality & availability (EN1). Regarding the impact categories, there is an equivalent incidence across all five topics (Quality standards & competitiveness, Farm economics & resilience, Resource quality & availability, Community well-being & collaboration, and Income & Livelihood).

FIGURE 12. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES LOCATED IN "REGION 1"

Appendix E can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Sustainable policies & regulations” and “Governance & political environment” heavily influence trade activities. Furthermore, “Standards & agreements” heavily influence processing and trade activities.

In the Human dimension, “Income & livelihood” heavily influence production and processing activities.

In the Social dimension, “Community well-being & collaboration”, “Social & gender inequalities”, and “Societal awareness & measurement” heavily influence trade activities.

In the Environmental dimension, “Resource quality & availability” heavily influence production activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, “Support services & measures” heavily influence trade activities. On the other hand, “Quality standards & competitiveness” are heavily impacted by trade activities.

CS located in Latin America and the Caribbean.

In contrast, within the group of CS located in the UN SDG region “Latin America and the Caribbean” (Fig. 13), the most striking elements are, in terms of the three most frequent driver categories, Governance & political environment (PG4), Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), and Sustainable policies & regulations (PG2). On the other hand, the most frequent impact is Resource quality & availability (EN1).

FIGURE 13. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES LOCATED IN "REGION 2"

Appendix F can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, "Standards & agreements" heavily influence production and consumption activities; furthermore, "Sustainable policies & regulations" heavily influence production, trade, and consumption activities. On the other hand, "Government support & expenditure" are heavily impacted by production, processing, trade, and consumption activities.

In the Human dimension, "Food security & nutrition" heavily influence consumption activities and are heavily impacted by trade, and consumption activities. In the Social dimension, "Demographics" heavily influence production activities; furthermore, "Social & gender inequalities" are heavily impacted by production and processing activities. On the other hand, "Land tenure/ ownership rights" heavily influence production activities and are heavily impacted by production, trade, and consumption activities.

In the Environmental dimension, "Resource quality & availability" heavily influence production activities and are heavily impacted by consumption activities. On the other hand, "Resource efficiency" are heavily impacted by trade and consumption activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, "Support services & measures" heavily influence production activities; furthermore, "Quality standards & competitiveness" heavily influence trade activities. On the other hand, "trade systems & market dynamics" are heavily influence by trade and consumption activities.

CS located in Northern Africa and Western Asia.

Concerning the group of CS located in the UN SDG region “Northern Africa and Western Asia” (Fig. 14), the most striking elements are, in terms of the three most frequent driver categories, the same as for “Latin America and the Caribbean” located CS - Governance & political environment (PG4), Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), and Sustainable policies & regulations (PG2). On the other hand, the most frequent impact is Income & Livelihood (H1).

FIGURE 14. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES LOCATED IN "REGION 3"

Appendix G can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Governance & political environment” heavily influence trade activities.

In the Social dimension, “Community well-being & collaboration” and “Social & gender inequalities” heavily influence production activities.

In the Environmental dimension, “Climate” heavily influences production activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, “Support services & measures” and “Farm economics & resilience” are heavily impacted by production activities.

CS located in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Lastly, within the group of CS located in the UN SDG region “Sub-Saharan Africa” (Fig. 15), the most striking elements are, in terms of the three most frequent driver categories, Trade systems & market dynamics (EM1), Governance & political environment (PG4), and Community well-being & collaboration (S1). On the other hand, in terms of the three most frequent impacts, Income & Livelihood (H1), Farm economics & resilience (EM4), and Labor & Employment (S3).

FIGURE 15. DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE IN CASE STUDIES LOCATED IN "REGION 4"

Appendix H can be consulted for more details on the degree of influence of contextual elements on agrifood value chain activities, and vice versa. For illustration purposes, we point to the drivers and impacts with a high degree of influence within the Agricultural Trade System.

In the Policy & Governance dimension, “Sustainable policies & regulations” and “Governance & political environment” heavily influence production activities. On the other hand, “Government support & expenditure” are heavily impacted by production activities.

In the Human dimension, “Food security & nutrition” heavily influence consumption activities. On the other hand, “Income & livelihood” are heavily impacted by production activities.

In the Social dimension, “Labour & employment” heavily influence production activities.

Finally, in the Economy & market dimension, “Macroeconomic factors” heavily influence processing activities; furthermore, “Quality standards & competitiveness” heavily influence consumption activities. On the other hand, “Trade systems & market dynamics” and “Support services & measures” are heavily impacted by production activities.

Provide an overview of MATS insights on the linkages between agricultural trade and sustainability dimensions.

Upon analyzing the set of MATS case studies, elements have been identified across all five contextual dimensions, confirming the existing linkages between agrifood value chain activities and its embedding context.

As shown in Figure 16, among the evaluated dimensions, the Economy & Market dimension stands out with 28% of the elements addressed by the set of case studies, followed by the Social dimension with 24%, and the Human dimension with 15%. Meanwhile, the Environmental dimension exhibits the lowest percentage at 10%.

FIGURE 16. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES SYSTEMIC ANALYSIS – ELEMENTS ADDRESSED BY DIMENSION

Figure 17 shows the results of the analysis of the frequency with which each case study' addressed elements (drivers and impacts of agricultural trade) within each dimension. The Policy & Governance dimension emerges as the highest number of elements acting as drivers, totaling 97, followed by the Economy & Market dimension with 79 elements. In terms of elements acting as impacts, the Human dimension takes the lead with 54 elements, followed by the Social dimension, and the Economic & Market dimension, each with 48 elements.

Figure 17. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES SYSTEMIC ANALYSIS – DRIVERS AND IMPACTS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE BY DIMENSION

Figure 18 shows the percentage distribution of topics across the five dimensions. Notably, the highest percentage values, exceeding 10%, are attributed to Trade systems & market dynamics (13%) and Governance & political environment (12%).

Figure 18. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES SYSTEMIC ANALYSIS – TOPICS OF AGRICULTURAL TRADE BY DIMENSION

The heatmap in Table 4 depicts the elements addressed by MATS case studies, illustrating the number of case studies addressing each element, either as a driver or as an impact of agricultural trade.

Among the drivers most addressed within MATS – in more than 11 CS – are “Power relations/ imbalances” in the Policy and Governance dimension, “Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders” in the Social dimension, and “Trade agreements & policy frameworks” in Economy and Market dimension. In contrast, among the impacts, the emphasis is on “Household incomes” and “Food and Nutrition Security” in the Human dimension, and “Productivity and Profitability” in the Economy and Market dimension.

TABLE 4. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES SYSTEMIC ANALYSIS - HEATMAP OF THE ADDRESSED ELEMENTS

Dimensions	Topics	Elements	Driver	Impact
	Standards & agreements	Social & environmental standards		
		Health & safety standards		
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Energy policies		
		Land use policies		
		Water policies		
		Food policies		
		Animal welfare regulations		
		Environmental regulations (climate adaptation & resilience)		
		Legal framework on equity & non-discrimination		
		Labour policies & legislations		
		Government support & expenditure	Public Social Spending	
	Resource flow for sustainable development			
	Official flows/ financial support to the agricultural sector			
	Governance & political environment	Governance structures & mechanisms		
		Power relations/ imbalances		
		Knowledge dynamics in agrifood sector governance		
		Agency in decision-making		
		Political crisis and corruption		
		Political leadership		
		Policy coherence		
	Income & livelihood	Household incomes		
		Household expenditure		
		Livelihoods		
		Poverty rates		
	Food security & nutrition	Food & nutrition security		
		Dietary changes		
		Food preferences		
	Financial security	Financial security		
	Human rights & well-being	Human rights		
		Access to basic services		
		Human wellbeing		
		Human health		
	Knowledge & skills	Knowledge & Skills		

Dimensions	Topics	Elements	Driver	Impact
	Community well-being & collaboration	Social welfare & social protection		
		Social norms & traditions		
		Local development		
		Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders		
	Social & gender inequalities	Social inequalities		
		Gender equality		
	Labor & employment	Employment rates		
		Informal employment		
		Labour rights & working conditions		
		Child labour		
		Youth labour		
		Hourly earnings of employee		
	Societal awareness & measurement	Societal awareness & measurement		
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Research, innovation, and technology		
		Knowledge dynamics & capacity building		
		Good practices		
		Agriculture area under productive & sustainable agriculture		
Social crises	Conflicts & humanitarian crises			
Land tenure/ ownership rights	Land tenure/ Ownership rights			
Demographics	Migration			
	Resource quality & availability	Land degradation/ restoration		
		Change of land use		
		Deforestation		
		Natural resources availability & quality		
		Competition for productive resources		
		Environmental degradation		
		Air Quality		
		Water quality		
		Water stress/ crisis		
	Resource efficiency	Material footprint		
		Access to environmental-friendly technology		
	Climate	Climate change		
		Climate impact, adaptation/ mitigation		
		GHG emissions		

Dimensions	Topics	Elements	Driver	Impact
	Trade systems & market dynamics	Globalization		
		International market dynamics		
		Market access		
		Aid for trade commitments		
		Trade agreements & policy frameworks		
		Trade openness		
		Trade economic growth		
		Demand for agri-food products		
		Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures		
		Non-Tariff measures in agricultural trade		
		Price volatility		
		Volume traded		
		Support services & measures	Access to credits & funding	
	Information access & transparency			
	Public & private investments			
	Fossil-fuel prices or subsidies			
	Macroeconomic factors	Economic growth		
		Exchange rates & inflation rates		
	Farm economics & resilience	Economic resilience		
		Productivity & profitability		
		Farmers' share of food prices		
	Taxation	Taxation in the agri-food value chains		
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Voluntary standards		
		Competitiveness		

Strategic actions/ pathways to transform the agricultural trade, maximizing its contributions to SDGs.

Engage with MATS case studies' complexity and particularities to identify leverage points and strategic actions to transform the agricultural trade system toward advancing the SDGs.

The following case studies' factsheets summarize the leverage points for transitioning to more sustainable agricultural trade. Potential actions for change are formulated as interventions at the identified strategic points, and the contextual conditions and particularities of the case studies that would enable them are described.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agency in decision-making	Enhance stakeholder participation in policy design to clarify implementation frameworks and ensure inclusive decision-making.	Enhancing stakeholder participation in policy development can avoid misunderstandings and unrest among value chain actors, which can hinder the implementation of policy frameworks such as the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP).
Governance structures and mechanisms	Enhance governance structures to change the dynamics of agrifood systems and contribute to sustainable development.	Improving the governance structure can help diminish the dominance of intermediaries as the primary market channel for coffee sales in Eastern and Central Uganda, potentially leading to significant changes in the coffee market dynamics and increasing farmers' incomes.
Policy coherence	Simplify bureaucratic procedures to enhance farmers' active participation and engagement in food systems.	Simplified bureaucratic procedures can enable farmers to readily access and register for a wide array of services, resources, or opportunities, thereby enhancing their active participation and engagement in agricultural activities.
Food policies	Enhance financial and technical support for farmers to meet sector requirements and adopt sustainable practices.	Implementing the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP) has stirred unease among value chain actors, impeding its progress, mainly due to perceived high commercial levies such as coffee year subscription fees. In light of this, it is crucial to offer financial and technical support to assist farmers in meeting the requirements of the ASSP without feeling burdened by costs.
Official flows/ financial support to the agricultural sector	Promote investment in new infrastructure to strengthen the enforcement of regulations.	The decentralization of inspection and certification processes should be considered to enhance the applicability of the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP) through investments in new infrastructure.

“Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains in Uganda”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Integrating stakeholders along the value chain can foster fair trade practices, diminish reliance on a small group of dominant players, and bolster initiatives that empower local farmers and aggregators to have a stronger voice and bargaining power within the coffee value chain.
	Strengthen associativity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making processes and their access to markets with better prices.	Strengthening associativity and promoting farmer group membership can enhance coffee quality, leading to higher incomes for farmers through increased prices.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Foster information symmetry and transparency for consistent and clear information disclosure in transactions.	Fostering information transparency and digitization can maintain consistency and clarity in disclosing information across the coffee value chain. This allows consumers to access transparent details about sourcing practices, product attributes, coffee origins, production methods, and sustainability practices.
Trade agreements and policy frameworks	Strengthen protective policies to shield farmers from volatile world market prices.	Uganda has entered into several bilateral and multilateral trade agreements, which have positively impacted coffee exports. However, to mitigate the risks associated with trade liberalization, Uganda needs to nuance its policies to protect farmers from volatile world market prices.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Governance structures and mechanisms	Enhance governance structures to change the dynamics of agrifood systems and contribute to sustainable development.	Enhancing governance structures is essential for the coffee sector’s long-term sustainability and poverty reduction. This approach supports the establishment of initiatives such as the coffee industry stabilization fund, a coffee research institute, free coffee seedling production and distribution, the promotion of cooperative institutions, public-private partnerships, and the creation of political will for the development of the coffee industry.

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Knowledge & skills	Enhance farmers' knowledge and skills to bolster their bargaining power and participation in decision-making.	Enhancing farmers’ knowledge and skills for accessing financial services can bolster their bargaining power, enabling them to negotiate better terms, secure essential financial services and inputs, and participate more effectively in decisionmaking processes. This, in turn, can significantly improve their position within the coffee value chain.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Most of the coffee value chain actors work in isolation and fail to recognize the cumulated impact of their independence and interaction. So, integrating stakeholders along the value chain can foster collaboration, a shared vision, common principles, and coordinated efforts to effectively address challenges. This approach helps achieve a competitive advantage of the coffee value chain.
	Strengthen associativity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making processes and their access to markets with better prices.	With market liberalization of the coffee sector, the dominance of cooperative unions in the coffee sector waned, contrary to expectations. Strengthen associativity can improve market participation of smallholder farmers, increase farm incomes and reduce rural poverty, and ensure proper information flow amongst members in order to facilitate informed decision making.
Knowledge dynamics & capacity building	Enhance extension services to support sustainable production, enabling farmers to access to markets with better prices, thus improving their livelihoods.	Enhancing extension services can assist smallholder farmers in meeting standards that qualify for higher price premiums, increased incomes, and greater profits. This improvement not only improves livelihoods but also contributes significantly to poverty alleviation.
Research, innovation, and technology	Promote funding for R&D to generate new knowledge and technologies.	Most Tanzanian coffee farmers struggle with low production rates due to the absence of improved varieties. Promoting funding for R&D can enhance coffee variety production, addressing challenges such as low yields, high pest control costs, poor quality, and fluctuating market prices. Developing high-yield, pest-resistant coffee varieties that adapt well to local conditions is critical.

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Foster information symmetry and transparency for consistent and clear information disclosure in transactions.	Fostering symmetry and transparency of information ensures that all parties involved in a transaction have access to the same or similar information. By providing clear and accurate details about products, services, or transactions, smallholder farmers in the coffee value chain can fully benefit from fair trade programs.
Market access	Develop promotion and marketing strategies to strengthen the market access and visibility of agrifood products.	Strengthening market access and visibility involves promoting Tanzanian coffee at international trade fairs, exhibitions, and coffee competitions to enhance its presence and reputation in global markets. Additionally, developing robust branding and marketing campaigns can effectively showcase the unique qualities and origin of Tanzanian coffee.
Trade agreements and policy frameworks	Strengthen protective policies to shield farmers from volatile world market prices.	Nuancing trade policies to safeguard both cooperative farmers and coffee quality, fostering a more conducive business environment for cooperatives and smallholder farmers. By ensuring that private coffee buyers operate fairly and transparently, policies would contribute to safeguard the interests of smallholder farmers.
Voluntary standards	Promote Fair Trade accreditation to ensure sustainable production costs, fair wages, and good working conditions for farm workers.	Implementing fair trade standards for certified coffee production can offer smallholder farmers with higher prices that cover the average cost of sustainable agricultural production, access to financial services for agricultural investment, adoption of new technologies that are necessary for compliance with sustainability standards and protection against price fluctuations.
	Develop context-specific Fair Trade standards to reflect local conditions.	Developing context-specific standards can help Fair Trade better reflect local conditions and realities in different regions. This involves recognizing and accommodating variations in production practices, environmental conditions, and socio-economic contexts. Additionally, creating mechanisms for transparent information exchange between producers and consumers—such as detailed labeling, storytelling, and digital platforms that provide insights into the production process and farmers' lives—can enhance understanding and support.
	Streamline compliance costs with regulations and certification standards to support farmers economically.	Streamlining the cost of compliance with regulations and certification standards can offer essential support and resources to assist farmers in meeting these requirements without facing excessive financial burdens. This approach ensures that certification standards contribute to the economic sustainability of farmers, rather than hindering their success.
Taxation in the agrifood value chain	Promote taxation incentives to reduce administrative burdens and bolster domestic products competitiveness in the market	Officials at the coffee estates reported having to pay multiple taxes at various stages of the coffee value chain. Streamlining transaction taxes can significantly alleviate financial pressure on the coffee estates, improving their profitability and sustainability. Consolidating these multiple taxes into a single, more manageable tax could simplify compliance and reduce administrative burdens.

“Intra-EU trade, resilience, and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Governance structures and mechanisms	Integrate social sustainability standards into organizational change to ensure companies address and prioritize social sustainability.	Reshape how companies' approach and prioritize social sustainability to transition towards sustainability in the oats value chain by expanding involvement beyond dedicated sustainability units to include HR departments and the broader organizational structure.

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Processors and retailers wield significant influence due to their dominant position relative to farming and production capacity, impacting market prices in their favor during contract negotiations, to the detriment of producers. Integrating stakeholders along the value chain is vital for promoting equity and fairness in the agricultural supply chain. This implies to strengthen producer cooperatives and associations to negotiate collectively with processors and retailers enhances farmers' bargaining power, ensuring fairer contract terms, and thus improving economic viability for small farm operations.
Gender equality	Enhance women's participation, ownership, and representation in decisions to advance gender equality and women's empowerment in food systems.	Women's representation in decisions regarding the purchase, sale, or transfer of assets is currently low. Enhancing women's representation in these processes is essential for advancing gender equality and empowering women. Encouraging and supporting women to advocate for increased participation in decision-making processes is crucial. Additionally, providing women with access to financial services such as credit, savings, and insurance can economically empower them, facilitating investments in agricultural as-sets and promoting sustainable livelihoods.
Societal awareness & measurement	Shift the focus on food systems assessments to ensure the relevance and inclusivity of social aspects	Shifting the focus of food systems assessments to prioritize the inclusivity of social aspects within organizations can foster a balanced and holistic approach to data collection and reporting. This approach enables capturing both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of social impact, including factors such as workers' well-being, job satisfaction, and community engagement. Furthermore, it involves understanding stakeholders' perspectives and priorities regarding social impact to ensure relevance and inclusivity in assessments.

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Environmental regulations	Enhance environmental regulations to prevent deforestation, land degradation, and GHG emissions.	Nuancing regulations on manure application per hectare and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can unlock opportunities for herd expansion and agricultural productivity within environmental sustainability constraints. Adopting sustainable farming practices that minimize the environmental impact of dairy production is crucial.

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Knowledge dynamics & capacity building	Enhance extension services to support sustainable production, enabling farmers to access to markets with better prices, thus improving their livelihoods.	Farmers’ understanding of the environmental and climate impacts of dairy production is crucial for promoting sustainable practices and gaining consumer acceptance. Enhancing farmers’ knowledge and skills supports sustainable production methods and improves the perception of dairy farming among consumers. Achieving this involves developing and offering training programs that focus on sustainable agricultural practices, environmental impacts, and precision farming techniques. Additionally, creating and disseminating comprehensive resources such as guides, manuals, and online courses covering best practices in environmentally sustainable dairy farming will further support these efforts.

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Shift subsidies to performance-based models to contribute to sustainability.	Shifting subsidies to performance-based models can incentivize farmers to achieve specific outcomes related to sustainability, animal welfare, environmental stewardship, and ecosystem service preservation. This approach promotes efficiency improvements, encourages the adoption of more sustainable practices, supports farm consolidation and modernization efforts, and can foster local tourism opportunities, offering economic diversification.

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Governance structures and mechanisms	Enhance governance structures to change the dynamics of agrifood systems and contribute to sustainable development.	Promoting the establishment of public agencies dedicated to export promotion can significantly enhance efforts to support the development of the cassava, plantain, and goat value chains, leading to increased export opportunities and economic growth. These agencies can assist stakeholders in developing and promoting their brands in target export markets while fostering Public-Private Partnerships to ensure comprehensive and effective support across the value chains.
Food policies	Encourage policies that advocate for including local agrifood products in national Food and Nutrition Security strategies.	Developing a specific policy statement can encourage the enhancement of the role of goat products (goat meat and goat milk) in Ethiopia’s food and nutrition security strategy. This can be achieved by engaging with policymakers, agricultural stakeholders, and nutrition experts to advocate for their inclusion and highlight their nutritional benefits and economic potential.

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Access to credits & funding	Promote alternative financing mechanisms to reduce compliance costs and enhance productivity in small-scale farms.	Supporting the agricultural financial system can lead to more sustainable credit facilities and enhance the overall value chain of selected agri-food commodities. This can be achieved by creating financial products specifically designed for smallholder farmers and rural businesses and expanding the reach of financial services in rural areas through the establishment of more rural banks, microfinance institutions, and mobile banking options.
Public & private investments	Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability.	Promoting investment in environmentally friendly technology (ridge-terracing to trap rainwater and drip irrigation for banana and cocoa, sub-soiling to retain more water per cassava plant, and paddock grazing of goats) can lead to significant improvements in water retention, soil health, and efficient land use, which are critical factors for enhancing productivity and sustainability in agriculture. By focusing on these practices, farmers can achieve better yields, more efficient resource utilization, and a more resilient farming system.
Trade agreements and policy frameworks	Enhance domestic marketing policies for organized and competitive pricing.	Enhancing domestic marketing policies can lead to better-organized marketing systems, more efficient and competitive pricing. This can be achieved by developing and implementing consistent and transparent marketing policies that are regularly communicated to all stakeholders.

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Encourage the establishment of alliances/partnerships between food systems actors to foster collaboration and collectively address critical issues	Strengthening collaboration with non-state actors can effectively address various critical issues such as gender equality, pro-poor interventions, and climate change mitigation. Additionally, it can promote joint project investments between the government and the private sector.
		Strengthening linkages between research, extension services, and farmers can enhance the adoption of best practices, helping value chain agents improve yields, increase cost efficiency, and meet quality standards for accessing national and international markets.
Research, innovation, and technology	Promote funding for R&D to generate new knowledge and technologies.	Research institutions have been responsible for developing and providing farmers with new varieties and breeds of crops (cassava, banana, and cocoa) and animals (goats) tailored to different consumer requirements. However, increasing funding for R&D is essential to develop the next generation of breeds and varieties capable of adapting to climate change and evolving consumer preferences.
	Enhance the documentation of good practices to contribute to sustainable and profitable farming operations.	Improving the documentation of best practices can significantly enhance goat production systems' productivity, health, and profitability, thereby promoting more sustainable and successful farming operations.
Land tenure/ Ownership rights	Promote women's land ownership to advance gender equality and empower them as critical agents in the overall development of communities.	Promoting women's land ownership can enhance gender equality and improve access to financial products for women. Achieving this involves revising inheritance laws and property rights to eliminate gender discrimination. It also requires engaging community leaders and elders in discussions about the benefits of women owning land and how it can contribute to the community's economic development.

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Policy coherence	Strengthen coordination mechanisms between public agencies for greater cohesiveness, coherence, integration, and effectiveness.	Strengthening coordination mechanisms within ministries and agencies can help them work more cohesively, ensuring that policies are coherent, effectively implemented, and capable of driving sustainable agricultural development. This involves outlining clear roles, responsibilities, and collaborative strategies to ensure all policies are complementary and not contradictory.
Political leadership	Improve the dissemination and outreach of government initiatives to engage and benefit to a broader spectrum of stakeholders.	Enhancing the dissemination of government initiatives can boost awareness and participation in poultry sector programs, ensuring they reach and benefit a broader spectrum of stakeholders across the entire value chain. This involves engaging with poultry farmers, associations, cooperatives, and other stakeholders at the grassroots level to communicate information about government programs effectively.
Food policies	Support policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices to improve competitiveness.	Supporting policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices in Ghana can enhance the competitiveness and diversification of the agricultural sector, thereby contributing to economic development while safeguarding environmental and social standards. Such policies entail incorporating sustainability criteria into trade policies and industrial transformation agendas.
	Enhance financial and technical support for farmers to meet sector requirements and adopt sustainable practices.	Promote financial incentives or grants to poultry farmers to adopt renewable energy technologies and promote energy-efficient practices in their operations, aiming to reduce electricity consumption and alleviate the burden of high production costs.
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enhance policies that support fair labor practices and improve local community livelihoods to contribute to inclusive and sustainable agricultural growth.	Policies supporting fair labor practices and improving local community livelihoods contribute to inclusive and sustainable agricultural growth by prioritizing the needs and rights of various stakeholders, including local communities, smallholder farmers, marginalized groups, and poultry sector workers. Strategies should focus on promoting gender equality and youth participation in agriculture through targeted interventions, training programs, and capacity-building initiatives.

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	By integrating stakeholders throughout the value chain, smallholder farmers can enhance their bargaining power and market competitiveness. This entails establishing fair and transparent market mechanisms that ensure smallholder farmers have equitable access to essential resources such as feed, veterinary services, financing, and technology.
Research, innovation, and technology	Promote funding for R&D to generate new knowledge and technologies.	Promoting funding for R&D can generate new knowledge and technologies that advance the poultry industry. Providing training and education on modern farming practices, disease prevention, and business management empowers smallholder farmers to enhance productivity and resilience. This approach supports the development of comprehensive strategies and initiatives to address critical challenges and foster positive change in Ghana's poultry sector.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Public & private investments	Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability.	Infrastructure for poultry and livestock production, processing and marketing remain a major challenge to the sector. Therefore, promoting investment in infrastructure development can facilitate the upgrading of processing facilities with modern equipment and technology. This not only enhances accessibility but also reduces transaction costs related to market access and transportation of feed and products.
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.	By generating targeted financial instruments, policies can protect poultry farmers from price volatility by mitigating the rising costs of essential feed ingredients such as soybean meal, corn and fishmeal.
Taxation in the agri-food value chain	Promote taxation incentives to reduce administrative burdens and bolster domestic products competitiveness in the market	Help alleviate poultry producers' financial stress by promoting tax deductions or accelerated depreciation for investments in technology and expenses related to improving transportation logistics. And by developing strategies that directly address high feed-related costs (e.g., feed formulation optimization, exploration of feed alternatives, price negotiation, or vertical integration).

“The living income differential for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agency in decision-making	Enhance stakeholder participation in policy design to clarify implementation frameworks and ensure inclusive decision-making.	Enhancing stakeholder participation in policy development can avoid misunderstandings and unrest among value chain actors (including farmers and NGOs), which can hinder the implementation of policy frameworks such as Living Income Differential (LID).
Political leadership	Enhance due diligence and accountability mechanisms to ensure projects and regulations account for socioeconomic and environmental risks and impacts.	Lack of regulation leads to a race to the bottom regarding taking corporate responsibility for human rights violations in the value chain. Therefore, binding regulations must be promoted in consumer countries that oblige companies to conduct comprehensive human rights due diligence along their value chains. This includes risk assessment, implementation of preventive measures, and remediation when violations occur.
Environmental regulations	Enhance environmental regulations to prevent deforestation, land degradation, and GHG emissions.	Enhancing environmental regulations can enforce laws that prevent deforestation and land degradation in cocoa-producing areas by developing robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance with sustainable practices and penalize illegal activities.
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Promote and enforce “no child labor” to foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children.	Promoting and enforcing “no child labor” in sustainability policies and standards can eradicate child labor and foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children. This involves conducting awareness campaigns on the harmful effects of child labor and the importance of education and child welfare, targeting both parents and the wider community, along with government initiatives that provide financial assistance or subsidies to farmers in times of low income, which helps alleviate the need for child labor to supplement family income.

“The living income differential for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Encourage the establishment of alliances/partnerships between food systems actors to foster collaboration and collectively address critical issues	Encouraging the establishment of cocoa producer alliances can facilitate coordination on crucial aspects such as supply management, demand projections, and price negotiations. This involves setting up channels for regular exchange of information and data among cocoa-producing countries, covering production forecasts, market trends, and consumption patterns. Additionally, harmonizing export policies, tariffs, and quotas is essential to prevent distortions in global cocoa markets and ensure fair competition among producers.
	Strengthen associativity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making processes and their access to markets with better prices.	Strengthening associativity and promoting farmer group membership can cultivate an environment of inclusivity and mutual respect within cocoa cooperatives. This ensures that every member feels empowered to express their viewpoints and engage in collective decision-making processes. Additionally, this entails enhancing financial management practices within cocoa cooperatives to guarantee accurate budgeting, meticulous accounting, and transparent financial operations.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Foster information symmetry and transparency for consistent and clear information disclosure in transactions.	Fostering symmetry and transparency information by enforcing accountability in the cocoa sector through regular audits and inspections to monitor compliance with market regulations and protect the interests of all market participants. Involve a broad range of stakeholders, including cocoa farmers, civil society organizations, and industry representatives, in the decision-making process to ensure inclusivity and fairness.
Competitiveness	Implement practices that add value to agrifood products to ensure producing countries receive fair and equitable prices in both national and international markets.	Nuancing agricultural and food policies can promote local processing of cocoa and other commodities to capture more value along the supply chain and create additional employment opportunities. Additionally, advocating for fair trade practices and market access reforms is essential to ensure that producing countries receive fair and equitable prices for their commodities.

“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Policy coherence	Adjust international regulations to cope with the particularities of food system challenges in different regions.	Promoting adjustments to policy regulations at the WTO and EPA levels can address the unique challenges West African nations face in safeguarding their dairy systems by ensuring transparency and accountability in implementing trade policies to build stakeholder trust.
	Strengthen coordination mechanisms between public agencies for greater cohesiveness, coherence, integration, and effectiveness.	Infrastructure investment can be crucial for upgrading milk collection centers, processing plants, and storage facilities. This effort necessitates the establishment of coordination mechanisms between government agencies, industry stakeholders, and development partners to effectively integrate policy measures into the broader framework of the ECOWAS initiative.

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Equipping stakeholders with essential resources, knowledge, and alliances can counteract the influence of economic actors opposing changes in trade and tax policies that favor local milk production in the West African region. By engaging in evidence-based advocacy, fostering collaboration, and actively engaging with policymakers and regional institutions, stakeholders can effectively champion policy reforms that bolster the development of the local dairy sector, thereby contributing to sustainable economic growth and enhancing food security.

**“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa?
Proposals to West African and European actors”**

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enforce import restrictions policies and control measures to strengthen domestic production while fostering a shift toward sustainable food systems.	<p>Enforcing policies to ban or reduce palm oil imports can involve enacting legislation to ban the import of palm oil linked to deforestation. This can include a complete ban or targeted bans on palm oil from regions known for unsustainable practices. Additionally, setting strict quotas on the amount of palm oil that can be imported and gradually reducing these quotas over time can encourage a shift away from palm oil.</p> <p>Gradually strengthening import restrictions can provide the local dairy sector with the necessary time to adapt to shifts in demand and production capacity. Making imports of milk powder contingent upon processors integrating a specific proportion of local milk into their production processes can effectively boost the demand for local milk and bolster support for domestic producers.</p>

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agency in decision-making	Enhance stakeholder participation in policy design to clarify implementation frameworks and ensure inclusive decision-making.	Improving stakeholder participation in policy design can effectively address disputes from land negotiations and governance issues fairly and transparently. This involves providing access to information and actively involving communities in decision-making.
Governance structures and mechanisms	Enhance due diligence and accountability mechanisms to ensure projects and regulations account for socioeconomic and environmental risks and impacts.	Improving due diligence processes within development banks can ensure that loans for biofuel projects undergo comprehensive assessments of socioeconomic and environmental risks. This involves conducting thorough impact assessments and actively engaging with local communities throughout the project evaluation process.
	Promote remedy mechanisms to ensure justice, compensation, and support for rebuilding livelihoods.	Promoting remedy mechanisms can ensure communities receive justice, compensation, and the necessary support to rebuild and improve their livelihoods. This includes providing ongoing medical support and rehabilitation services to those affected by chemical exposure and environmental degradation and implementing environmental remediation projects to restore polluted water sources, soil, and ecosystems.
Political crisis and corruption	Strengthen anti-corruption regulations to ban corporate bribery and undue benefits to political leaders.	Companies often promise unique benefits to political leaders and their communities, using this leverage to pressure them into requalifying land at a lower price or obtaining additional water extraction permits. To counteract such practices, it is crucial to enforce anti-corruption policies that prohibit companies from engaging in bribery or offering undue benefits to political figures.
Energy policies	Nuance of EU bio-fuel production policies to prioritize sustainable production in producer countries.	Nuancing biofuel production policies can advocate for policy reforms at the EU level. These reforms should aim to revise biofuel mandates and incentives, monitor mechanisms, and prioritize sustainable production methods in producer countries. This includes minimizing environmental and social impacts by addressing issues such as land rights, labor rights, and conservation practices.
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and pro-protect workers' rights.	Enforcing labor regulations in producer countries can ensure compliance with safety standards and protection of workers' rights. Conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures and regular wage reviews are needed to enforce labor regulations.
Legal framework on equity and non-discrimination	Strengthen legal frameworks to guarantee the protection of Indigenous territorial rights.	Strengthening legal frameworks can guarantee the enforcement of existing laws that protect Indigenous land rights and ensure mandatory and meaningful consultation with Indigenous communities on matters affecting their land and resources.

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Foster information symmetry and transparency for consistent and clear information disclosure in transactions.	Enhancing reporting requirements can ensure the enforcement of publicly disclosing relevant information about bioethanol supply chains, including sourcing practices, environmental impacts, and stakeholder engagement. This strengthens symmetry and governs transparency within the supply chain.

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights.	Farm workers are unable to collectively bargain, have less access to grievance mechanisms, and less leverage on their working conditions. Therefore, encouraging companies to adopt policies supporting workers' rights to collectively bargain and to develop and implement accessible, transparent, and effective workplace grievance mechanisms.
Political leadership	Enhance enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance with human rights laws.	Enhancing enforcement mechanisms can ensure compliance with national legislation safeguarding human rights, including equity and non-discrimination. This involves effective monitoring, investigation, and imposition of penalties for violations. Integrating human rights considerations alongside environmental and due diligence factors contributes to fostering responsible and sustainable business practices.
Social & environmental standards	Advocate for international social standards to advance gender equality and labor rights.	Promoting and enforcing “no child labor” in sustainability policies and standards can eradicate child labor and foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children. This involves conducting awareness campaigns on the harmful effects of child labor and the importance of education and child welfare, targeting both parents and the wider community, along with government initiatives that provide financial assistance or subsidies to farmers in times of low income or crop failure, which helps alleviate the need for child labor to supplement family in-come.

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Promote pricing transparency and traceability systems to ensure fair compensation for farmers.	Enhancing transparency and pricing mechanisms enables the tracking and documentation of coffee quality and pricing throughout the value chain, from farmers to middlemen and exporters. This fosters the adoption of transparent pricing practices, such as fair trade or direct trade, ensuring farmers receive equitable compensation for their produce.

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Involving stakeholders across the coffee value chain promotes open and honest communication, building trust and transparency in decision-making. It enables collaborative identification and assessment of risks affecting all stakeholders, from climate-related challenges to market fluctuations and supply chain disruptions.
Gender equality	Enhance women's participation, ownership, and representation in decisions to advance gender equality and women's empowerment in food systems.	Promoting women's land ownership includes facilitating access to and control over land resources through land redistribution and titling programs. This entails advocating for equal land ownership rights for women, including reforms in inheritance and property registration laws that recognize and safeguard women's land rights. Additionally, fostering women's participation in coffee sales is crucial for their economic and social empowerment within coffee-growing communities.
Land tenure/ Ownership rights	Promote women's land ownership to advance gender equality and empower them as critical agents in the overall development of communities.	Promoting women's land ownership involves facilitating access to and control over land resources through land redistribution and titling programs. This entails advocating for equal land ownership rights for women and reforms in inheritance and property registration laws to recognize and safeguard women's land rights. Additionally, fostering women's participation in coffee sales is crucial for their economic and social empowerment within coffee-growing communities.

“Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.	Providing government grants and subsidies can facilitate access to capital specifically for technology adoption in the beef sector. This includes investing in infrastructure improvements to enhance the efficient movement and processing of beef products, making the industry more sustainable and competitive.
	Enforce import restrictions policies and control measures to strengthen domestic production while fostering a shift toward sustainable food systems.	Enhancing the implementation of tariffs and quotas on imported beef can make it less competitive compared to locally produced beef and limit the amount of beef that can be imported. This ensures a larger market share for local producers, helping to mitigate the negative impact of low-priced imports and strengthen the local beef production industry.
Competitiveness	Implement practices that add value to agrifood products to ensure producing countries receive fair and equitable prices in both national and international markets.	Encouraging the implementation of sustainability labelling for beef can attract consumer attention to sustainable products, influencing purchasing decisions and increasing access to international markets where sustainability is a key criterion. Additionally, it can enhance brand reputation and foster customer loyalty.

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Food policies	Support policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices to improve competitiveness.	Supporting policies promoting good practices can ensure that certification standards explicitly require adopting sustainable farming techniques, animal welfare standards, and environmental conservation. Promoting good practices involves implementing regular audits and inspections to ensure certified farms consistently adhere to them.
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights.	Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews.
Legal framework on equity and non-discrimination	Promote gender-sensitive policies to prevent gender discrimination.	Promoting gender-sensitive policies can establish and enforce measures that prevent discrimination based on gender in hiring, promotions, and salary decisions. Additionally, these policies should develop and implement strategies that foster an inclusive workplace culture where diversity is valued, and gender equality is prioritized.

Human capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Knowledge & skills	Strengthen farmers' knowledge and skills to support sustainable production.	Strengthening farmers' knowledge and skills is pivotal for promoting sustainable production practices and improving consumers acceptance of avocado and mango cultivation. Implementing targeted training programs on sustainable farming practices, environmental impacts, and cultivation techniques is essential. These efforts should be complemented by the development and dissemination of comprehensive resources such as guides, manuals, and online resources aimed at fostering best practices for environmentally sustainable agriculture.

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Research, innovation, and technology	Promote funding for R&D to generate new knowledge and technologies.	Increasing funding for R&D can prioritize innovative pest and disease management strategies and promote the adoption of new technologies and practices to boost overall crop productivity for mango and avocado cultivation. This will improve yields, reduce losses, and increase profitability for farmers, thereby fostering rural development and economic growth.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Public & private investments	Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability.	Promote investment in upgrading storage facilities such as cold warehouses and transportation infrastructure like roads and refrigerated trucks, while expanding capacity to accommodate higher volumes of produce and alleviate congestion.
Voluntary standards	Promote Fair Trade accreditation to ensure sustainable production costs, fair wages, and good working conditions for farm workers.	Strengthen fair trade standards for certified production can offer smallholder farmers with higher prices that cover the average cost of sustainable agricultural production, access to financial services for agricultural investment, adoption of new technologies that are necessary for compliance with sustainability standards and protection against price fluctuations.
Taxation in the agri-food value chain	Promote taxation incentives to reduce administrative burdens and bolster domestic products competitiveness in the market	Promoting tax incentives, such as deductions or credits for investments in technology, infrastructure, and sustainable practices, can improve access to financing and encourage more investment in the sector. This also involves providing clear and consistent guidelines for businesses to follow, minimizing uncertainty and reducing the risk of incurring additional costs.

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agency in decision-making	Enhance stakeholder participation in policy design to clarify implementation frameworks and ensure inclusive decision-making.	Engaging stakeholders along the value chain can ensure the active participation of local communities, previously disadvantaged individuals, wine farmers, government agencies, NGOs, and other relevant parties in decision-making processes. This approach incorporates diverse needs and perspectives, fosters strong community engagement, builds trust, and ensures initiatives are relevant and beneficial to the local population.
Food policies	Promote price premiums to boost compliance and product quality.	Promoting price premiums can incentivize producers to invest in compliance measures, enhancing the overall quality of their wine. By endorsing wine exports that adhere to specific quality, sustainability, or social responsibility standards, these premiums help offset compliance costs, making it financially viable for producers to prioritize quality and sustainability initiatives. Price premiums also encourage continuous improvement in production practices and enhance profit margins and competitiveness in the international market.
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights.	Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews. This will help to reduce the gap between VSS compliant and non-compliant wine farms.
Land use policies	Nuance land policies to ensure local socio-economic legislation supports ownership transformation.	Nuance land policies to ensure local socioeconomic legislation provides the essential support and flexibility to address challenges and adapt to evolving circumstances. This will facilitate meaningful ownership transformation and the inclusion of previously disadvantaged individuals while promoting sustainable development and ensuring compliance with socioeconomic standards.
Social & environmental standards	Advocate for international social standards to advance gender equality and labor rights.	Advocating for international policies on social standards can play a pivotal role in advancing gender equality and labor rights within the agricultural sector. By developing and enforcing labor regulations tailored to address gender disparities, such as ensuring equal pay for equal work and safeguarding against discrimination, we can foster inclusive growth in rural communities.

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Human capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Knowledge & skills	Strengthen farmers' knowledge and skills to support sustainable production.	The wine sector requires comprehensive training and education for farm workers to foster sustainable production practices. Enhancing their knowledge and skills involves developing and implementing tailored training programs focused on agricultural techniques, business management, and financial literacy. These initiatives empower farm workers and contribute to the enhancement of working conditions.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Access to credits & funding	Promote alternative financing mechanisms to reduce compliance costs and enhance productivity in small-scale farms.	Improving financial support for farmers can alleviate compliance costs. This assistance can manifest in diverse ways, including offering favorable loan terms to facilitate on-farm investments in social infrastructure and training programs.
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.	Improving financial support for farmers can alleviate compliance costs. This assistance can manifest in diverse ways, including covering audit expenses through subsidies.
Voluntary standards	Promote Fair Trade accreditation to ensure sustainable production costs, fair wages, and good working conditions for farm workers.	Promoting fair trade certification schemes can ensure farm workers receive fair wages and working conditions, encouraging consumers to support ethically produced agricultural products. Additionally, supporting living wage campaigns aims to establish wages enabling farm workers to meet basic needs like food, shelter, healthcare, and education. Promoting fair trade accreditation can ensure adherence to social standards valued by target niche markets, encompassing certifications related to fair labor practices, environmental sustainability, and community development. This effort involves crafting a compelling brand narrative around ethical sourcing, sustainability, and community engagement. Emphasizing the wine product's unique social and ethical attributes can set it apart from competitors. Additionally, maintaining transparency in the wine supply chain and production processes is crucial, providing consumers with clear information about the social standards adhered to and the impact of their purchasing decisions.

“Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”

Policy and governance

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Labour policies, regulations & legislations	Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights.	Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews.
		Promoting the implementation of minimum wage policies can ensure fair compensation for farm workers in Algeria and Zimbabwe, while strengthening legal protections to prevent exploitation and ensure fair treatment. More equitable pay structures can contribute to long-term sustainability and social stability in farming communities.
		Nuancing retirement age policies involves considering a gradual increase in retirement age to match rising life expectancies, thus safeguarding the sustainability of retirement systems. This entails implementing measures to alleviate poverty and enhance access to essential resources for older individuals, ensuring a dignified quality of life in retirement while also fostering opportunities for them to continue contributing as active and productive members of the workforce.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.	Encouraging price support mechanisms can offer targeted subsidies to dairy farmers in regions where milk prices fail to cover production costs, thereby offsetting losses and ensuring farm viability. This involves ongoing monitoring of milk prices and production costs to pinpoint imbalances and implement corrective measures, as necessary.

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Governance structures and mechanisms	Enhance due diligence and accountability mechanisms to ensure projects and regulations account for socioeconomic and environmental risks and impacts.	Enhancing transparency and accountability mechanisms can ensure that all information re-lated to the Authorization of Native Vegetation Conversion is publicly accessible, including applications, approvals, and associated documents. This involves establishing clear lines of accountability within regulatory bodies specifying roles and responsibilities for each authorization process stage. Furthermore, mechanisms should be established for the public and civil society organizations to report suspected illegal deforestation activities, ensuring these re-ports are taken seriously and investigated promptly.
Political crisis and corruption	Strengthen anti-corruption regulations to ban corporate bribery and undue benefits to political leaders.	Local leaders in Brazil report corrupting authorities like notaries and judges to validate fake land titles. Strengthening anti-corruption regulations can enhance the enforcement of laws designed to prevent corruption, including imposing strict penalties on companies, political leaders, notaries, and judges involved in unethical practices. Additionally, it is essential to establish monitoring mechanisms to track corporate and governmental activities related to land use and resource extraction.
Policy coherence	Adjust international regulations to cope with the particularities of food system challenges in different regions.	Promoting the refinement of the definition of savanna landscapes within EU regulations can involve broadening definitions and advocating for the inclusion of “other wooded land” and “natural grasslands” within the criteria for deforestation-free products (EUDR). This approach ensures comprehensive protection of savanna landscapes such as the Cerrado, underlining their importance for biodiversity conservation, water regulation, and ecosystem services.
Social & environmental standards	Enhance trade measures tied to environmental and social performance to promote sustainable practices in food systems.	Enhancing trade measures tied to environmental and social performance can be crucial to promoting sustainable land use practices. It’s imperative to advocate for stricter environmental and traceability requirements, especially to meet the demands of export markets, particularly China.

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Integrating stakeholders along the value chain can provide a collective voice by establishing institutions such as associations and grassroots organizations. These institutions can offer resources and bargaining power to poor family farmers, enabling them to negotiate more effectively with well-resourced and politically connected farmers.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Information access & transparency	Promote pricing transparency and traceability systems to ensure fair compensation for farmers.	Promoting robust traceability systems can create immutable records of soy origin, ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the supply chain. This includes the use of blockchain technology and clear labeling and documentation to distinguish certified products from non-certified ones.

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Power relations/ imbalances	Promote policies to prevent monopolistic practices.	Promoting policies to prevent monopolistic practices can address the issue of concentrated ownership of storage space contributing to higher urban potato prices, promoting fair competition, reducing costs, and improving market access for small-scale farmers and consumers alike.
Food policies	Nuance international policies and design national provisions to enhance agricultural sovereignty.	Nuancing restrictive seed policies of the UPOV Convention can strengthen Egyptian agricultural sovereignty, support local farmers, and promote sustainable farming practices. Such measures could be complemented with provisions that allow smallholder farmers to save seed for non-commercial use and by increasing funding and support for national breeding programs focused on developing varieties adapted to local conditions.
	Support policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices to improve competitiveness.	Nuancing agricultural and food policies can facilitate a transition towards a more comprehensive, sustainable, and self-reliant agricultural system. This approach reduces dependence on imported inputs and large agricultural companies, fostering a resilient and equitable agricultural sector.

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Knowledge & skills	Enhance farmers' knowledge and skills to bolster their bargaining power and participation in decision-making.	Small-scale farmers frequently face challenges due to their limited bargaining power, often leaving them at the mercy of traders or intermediaries who control over prices and exert significant pressure on them to sell. Strengthening farmers' knowledge and skills is crucial as it empowers them to negotiate from a position of strength. This enhanced bargaining power enables farmers to secure better terms, devise effective marketing strategies, and establish fair contract farming arrangements. Engaging in transparent transactions with traders and intermediaries fosters fair trading practices, thereby reducing farmers' vulnerability to market exploitation.

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Social capital

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness, and safeguard livelihoods.	Engaging stakeholders along the value chain entails involving farmers from the outset of project planning and design to ensure their needs and livelihoods are considered. This collaborative approach fosters more successful and sustainable outcomes for both infrastructure projects and the agricultural communities they impact.

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Public & private investments	Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability.	Promoting investment in infrastructure development can garner government support and secure the necessary funding and resources to improve storage capacity for small farmers. This includes advocating for the inclusion of agricultural storage infrastructure in national and regional development plans and supporting the creation of agricultural innovation hubs that focus on developing and scaling affordable storage technologies.
Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures	Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.	Enhancing state subsidies can better support smallholder farmers by reintroducing targeted subsidies to provide financial relief and access to essential inputs such as fertilizers and seeds. Developing a tiered subsidy program that offers higher support levels for small and medium-sized farms compared to large commercial farms will ensure equitable resource distribution.

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Power relations/ imbalances	Promote policies to prevent monopolistic practices.	Promoting regulations to address monopolies and speculation involves strengthening anti-trust laws and fostering competition to ensure fair market access and pricing.
Land use policies	Strengthen land use regulations for enhanced sustainability, productivity, and resilience.	Strengthening land use planning and management regulations can involve the development of comprehensive land use plans to identify suitable areas for olive cultivation and promote diversification of agricultural activities. By doing so, Tunisia can enhance its olive farming sector’s sustainability, productivity, and resilience.
Water policies	Enforce regulations for sustainable water management.	Enforcing regulations for sustainable water management can promote sustainable agricultural practices, ensure water security, and safeguard the environment for future generations. This includes implementing restrictions on groundwater extraction and offering incentives for water-saving practices. Moreover, encouraging the adoption of water-efficient irrigation techniques, such as drip irrigation and micro-sprinklers, can significantly reduce water usage in olive oil production while maintaining crop productivity.

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders	Encourage the establishment of alliances/ partnerships between food systems actors to foster collaboration and collectively address critical issues	Promoting public-private partnerships can foster collaborative efforts to deliver cost-effective support services to smallholder farmers. Advocating for a reconsideration of government resource allocation ensures that support programs adequately address the needs of small-scale producers. This may entail providing subsidies or incentives to encourage private service providers to extend their reach to underserved communities.

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Economy and markets

Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
Access to credits & funding	Promote alternative financing mechanisms to reduce compliance costs and enhance productivity in small-scale farms.	Promoting alternative financing mechanisms for farmers can involve exploring options such as microfinance institutions, cooperatives, and community-based lending initiatives. These avenues can help fill the gap left by the withdrawal of government support, ultimately enhancing the resilience and productivity of small and medium-sized farms.
Trade agreements and policy frameworks	Strengthen protective policies to shield farmers from volatile world market prices.	Strengthening protective policies can diminish Tunisia's reliance on imported vegetable oils, bolster the surplus of exportable olive oil, and mitigate vulnerability to global market fluctuations. This entails negotiating favorable trade agreements to secure stable markets for olive oil exports and reliable sources for vegetable oil imports. Additionally, it involves developing policies that strike a balance between the export of olive oil and domestic consumption needs.
Competitiveness	Implement practices that add value to agrifood products to ensure producing countries receive fair and equitable prices in both national and international markets.	Promoting value-added olive oil products can drive the establishment of modern processing facilities in Tunisia, focused on refining crude olive oil into higher-value offerings such as extra virgin olive oil or diversified products like flavored oils and cosmetics, aimed at broadening revenue streams. Simultaneously, cultivating a strong brand identity for Tunisian olive oil in target markets becomes paramount, emphasizing its exceptional quality, authenticity, and distinctive flavor profiles.

Provide an overview of MATS findings on leverage points to build a more sustainable agricultural trade that contribute to advance the SDGs.

Figure 19 summarizes the leverage points identified by MATS case studies, and the information provided on potential transition pathways and policy recommendations to foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of agricultural trade on environmental sustainability and human well-being. This figure shows that the identified leverage points correspond to aspects linked to policy and governance, social, and economy and markets dimensions (incl. investments). It also shows that acting on these strategic points would impact elements linked to the five dimensions.

On the other hand, Figure 19 shows the SDG indicators MATS case studies consider related to their scope and findings, in particular to the issues and strategic actions/ pathways identified and prioritized by them to transform agricultural trade.

The five donut charts illustrate the number of case studies that identified different SDG indicators as relevant and organize them around the five dimensions of the MATS analytical framework. Most of MATS case studies cover SDG indicators linked to the five contextual dimensions – from 9 covering policy-related indicators, to 13 covering economy-related ones – which confirms their systemic nature at the level of scope and expected results. The results go from one CS for several SDG indicators to 11 CS for SDG 2.3.2 “Average income of small-scale food producers” and SDG 1.1.1 “Proportion of population living below the international poverty line”.

FIGURE 19. LEVERAGE POINTS AND PATHWAYS TO TRANSFORM THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM

SDGs related to policy & governance

SDGs related to the human dimension

SDGs related to the social dimension

SDGs related to economy and market

SDGs related to the environmental dimension

FIGURE 20. SDG INDICATORS LINKED TO THE FIVE CONTEXTUAL DIMENSIONS

Linkages with Trade4SDG & VC4DE

The case study synthesis was also integrating insights from CS-level interactions with Trade4SDG and VC4Dev. Two case studies were identified for this purpose, since they apply to the same/ overlapping regional and commodity context in both consortia (MATS and Trade4SDG):

First, the case study 5 located Ghana, where MATS partner UPM and the local partner CSIR-Science and Technology Policy Research Institute, exchanged with Trade4SDG partner ISSER – Institute of Statistical, Social & Economic Research (ISSER), from the University of Ghana.

Second, the case study 15 located in Tunisia, where MATS partner TNI has begun a fruitful collaboration with Trade4SD partner, CREA (Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Italy) upon discovery that both partners have worked on a case study of the trade in olive oil between Tunisia and the EU. TNI shared an early draft of their case study report with CREA who subsequently referenced and integrated TNI's findings into their own case study report, notably around the structure of the olive oil value chain and the ecological impact of olive tree monocultures. The findings of the two reports mutually reinforce and strengthen one another and we have agreed in an online follow-up conversation to identify a number of spaces where we can jointly present and disseminate these messages. As a first step, TNI has invited CREA to present their case study during an online workshop organised by MATS on 1 March on the 'Legal Dimensions of Agricultural Trade and Sustainability'. There are also interesting points of divergence/discussion between TNI and CREA in our respective analysis. CREA has a more positive assessment of the DCFTA between the EU and Tunisia, while TNI has produce a more critical account of how this has progressed so far. This opens up the door

for fruitful debate on how sustainability and policy coherence for development can best be centered in the free trade agreement.

Furthermore, MATS CS#2 (oats) cooperated with VC4Dev, by applying the VC4Dev social matrix profile to the MATS oats case study (capturing also social value chain resilience, here in the context of a developed economy context), the outcome of which is visible in Appendix I.

Conclusion

This deliverable provides a systematic synthesis of the 15 case studies and their results, following a three-phase methodological approach newly developed in this Deliverable. This approach takes into account information and analyses from prior MATS tasks, including overarching analytical guidance (MATS analytical framework), and methodological case-based guidelines developed as part of the ongoing or finalized Work Packages work (WP1 to WP6). The key objectives were to (i) enable comparability and transferability of insights – across case studies, commodities, regions, governance issues, sustainability indicators, etc. – within a broad range of methodological approaches, (ii) provide insights into the robustness of CS-level results, and (iii) highlight the novelty of insights for policy solutions, resulting from the mixed- methods approach, and visualized through diverse graphic tools.

As a result, the output from this Deliverable is envisaged as a valuable input for the ongoing development and finalization of the transition pathways and policy recommendations (WP5), as well as stimuli for the ongoing society-stakeholder-policy dialogue (dissemination and communication, WP6).

From a systems perspective, striking was the role that certain elements within the political, social, and economic dimensions play as both key drivers and powerful levers for achieving more equitable, sustainable, fair, and competitive agricultural trade and contributing to human rights and well-being. Among these elements, we highlight policy, regulatory, and legal frameworks; infrastructure and technology development and investment; social and environmental sustainability standards; various forms of social cohesion, collaboration, integration, and partnership; research and development services tailored to farmers' needs; and trade rules and regimes.

We believe it is worth highlighting that case studies, although many strongly focused on improving the competitiveness of small-scale farmers, also jointly pointed to the need to improve food self-sufficiency and consider socially undesirable impacts that come along with a strong focus on exports. Thus, this deliverable highlights the need to analyze and recognize the viewpoints of diverse agents and the power imbalances that lead to maintaining food regimes that are desirable only for certain groups.

Ultimately, the converging themes and insights from this deliverable will contribute to a deeper understanding of the conditions for resilient and sustainable agricultural value chains and trade, highlight the usefulness and transferability of an integrated multi-model case-based approach, as well as laying bare the difficulties and benefits of a multi-methods assessment of the interconnections (drivers and impacts) between agricultural trade, investments, sustainability, and development.

As mentioned above, this deliverable is strongly linked to MATS' upcoming work on WP3, WP5, and WP6. Regarding WP3, this deliverable provides grounded-in-practice information to identify leverage points and levers to achieve more sustainable agricultural trade (D3.7). Regarding WP5, it feeds into the derivation of context-sensitive transition pathways. Finally, it provides valuable information to feed discussions and joint reflections between civil society, researchers, decision makers, and other critical actors involved in agricultural trade for its transformation (WP6).

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APPENDIX A. LIST OF TOPICS AND ELEMENTS

DIMENSIONS	TOPICS	ELEMENTS
I. Policy, governance, and regulations	1. Standards & Agreements	Biodiversity agreements
		Social & environmental standards
		Health & safety standards
	2. Sustainable policies & regulations	Energy policies
		Land use policies
		Water policies
		Food policies
		Animal welfare regulations
		Environmental regulations (climate adaptation & resilience)
		Labour policies and legislations
	Legal framework on equity and non-discrimination	
	3. Government Support and Expenditure	Public Social Spending
		Resource flow for sustainable development
		Official flows/ financial support to the agricultural sector
	4. Governance and political environment	Governance structures and mechanisms
		Power relations/ imbalances
Knowledge dynamics in agrifood sector governance		
Agency in decision-making		
Political crisis and corruption		
Political leadership		
Policy coherence		
II. Human dimension	1. Income & Livelihood	Household incomes
		Household expenditure
		Livelihoods
		Poverty rates
	2. Food Security & Nutrition	Food & nutrition security
		Dietary changes
		Food preferences
	3. Financial security	Financial security
	4. Human Rights & Well-being	Human rights
		Access to basic services
		Human wellbeing
	Human health	
	5. Knowledge & Skills	Knowledge & skills

APPENDIX A. LIST OF TOPICS AND ELEMENTS

DIMENSIONS	TOPICS	ELEMENTS
III. Social dimension	1. Community well-being & collaboration	Social welfare & social protection
		Social norms & traditions
		Local development
		Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders
	2. Social & gender inequalities	Social inequalities
		Gender equality
	3. Labor & Employment	Employment rates
		Informal employment
		Labour rights & working conditions
		Child labour
		Youth labour
		Force labour
	4. Societal awareness & measurement	Hourly earnings of employee
		Societal awareness & measurement
	5. Innovative knowledge & good practices	Research, innovation, and technology
		Knowledge dynamics & capacity building
Good practices		
Agriculture area under productive and sustainable agriculture		
6. Social Crises	Conflicts & humanitarian crises	
7. Land tenure/ Ownership rights	Land tenure/ Ownership rights	
8. Demographics	Migration	
	Urbanization	
8. Demographics	Population growth	
	Changing age profiles	
IV. Environmental/ Natural capital	1. Resource quality & availability	Land degradation/ restoration
		Change of land use
		Deforestation
		Natural resources availability & quality
		Competition for productive resources
		Environmental degradation
		Air Quality
		Water quality
		Water stress/ crisis
	2. Resource efficiency	Material footprint
		Access to environmental-friendly technology
	3. Climate	Climate change
		Climate impact, adaptation/ mitigation
		GHG emissions
	4. Renewable energy	Renewable energy consumption

APPENDIX A. LIST OF TOPICS AND ELEMENTS

DIMENSIONS	TOPICS	ELEMENTS
V. Economy & Market	1. Trade systems & market dynamics	Globalization
		International Market Dynamics
		Market access
		Aid for trade commitments
		Trade agreements and policy frameworks
		Trade openness
		Trade economic growth
		Demand for agri-food products
		Volume traded
		Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures
		Non-Tariff measures in agricultural trade
		Price volatility
	2. Support services & measures	Access to credits & funding
		Public & private investments
		Fossil-fuel prices or subsidies
		Information access & transparency
	3. Macroeconomic factors	Economic growth
		Exchange rates and inflation rates
	4. Farm economics & resilience	Economic resilience
		Productivity & profitability
		Farmers' share of prices
	5. Taxation	Food loss & food waste
		Taxation in the agri-food value chain
	6. Quality standards and competitiveness	Voluntary standards
		Competitiveness

APPENDIX B. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING “OBJECTIVE 1”.

OBJECTIVE 1: Governance and trade regimes in support of sustainable development and human rights						
Dimension	Topics	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver				
	Government support & expenditure	Driver				
		Impact				
	Governance & political environment	Driver				
		Impact				
		Impact				
	Food security & nutrition	Driver				
		Impact				
	Financial security	Impact				
	Human rights & well-being	Driver				
		Impact				
	Knowledge & skills	Driver				

OBJECTIVE 1: Governance and trade regimes in support of sustainable development and human rights						
Dimension	Topics	Typology				
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Labor & employment	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social crises	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Land tenure/ ownership rights	Driver	➔			
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Resource quality & availability	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Resource efficiency	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Climate	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔

OBJECTIVE 1: Governance and trade regimes in support of sustainable development and human rights						
Dimension	Topics	Typology				
	Trade systems & market dynamics	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Support services & measures	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Macroeconomic factors	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Farm economics & resilience	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Taxation	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔

APPENDIX C. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING “OBJECTIVE 2”

OBJECTIVE 2: Social & human rights considerations for Sustainable Agricultural Trade						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver				
	Government support & expenditure	Impact				
	Governance & political environment	Driver				
	Food security & nutrition	Driver				
		Impact				
	Human rights & well-being	Driver				
		Impact				
Knowledge & skills	Driver					

OBJECTIVE 2: Social & human rights considerations for Sustainable Agricultural Trade						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Labor & employment	Driver	➔	➔	➔	
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Societal awareness & measurement	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔	➔		
Demographics	Driver	➔				
	Resource quality & availability	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Resource efficiency	Driver	➔		➔	➔
	Climate	Impact	➔		➔	➔

OBJECTIVE 2: Social & human rights considerations for Sustainable Agricultural Trade						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
		Impact				
	Support services & measures	Driver				
		Impact				
	Farm economics & resilience	Impact				
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Driver				
		Impact				

APPENDIX D. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN GROUPING "OBJECTIVE 3"

OBJECTIVE 3: Power imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver				
	Governance & political environment	Driver				
		Impact				

OBJECTIVE 3: Power imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Income & livelihood	Driver	➔		➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Food security & nutrition	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Human rights & well-being	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔		
	Labor & employment	Driver	➔		➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social crises	Impact	➔	➔	➔	
	Land tenure/ ownership rights	Driver	➔		➔	➔
Demographics	Driver	➔				

OBJECTIVE 3: Power imbalances within food systems governance leading to unsustainable paths						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
		Impact				
	Climate	Driver				
		Impact				
		Impact				
	Support services & measures	Driver				
		Impact				
	Macroeconomic factors	Driver				
	Farm economics & resilience	Driver				
		Impact				
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Driver				
Impact						

APPENDIX E. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN LOCATION GROUPING "REGION 1"

REGION 1: Europe and Northern America						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver				
	Government support & expenditure	Driver				
	Governance & political environment	Driver				
		Impact				
	Food security & nutrition	Driver				
	Knowledge & skills	Driver				
		Impact				
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver				
	Societal awareness & measurement					
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver				

REGION 1: Europe and Northern America						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
		Impact				
	Support services & measures	Driver				
	Farm economics & resilience	Driver				
		Impact				
	Taxation	Driver				
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Impact				

APPENDIX F. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN LOCATION GROUPING "REGION 2"

REGION 2: Latin America and the Caribbean						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver				
	Government support & expenditure	Impact				
	Governance & political environment	Driver				
		Impact				
	Food security & nutrition	Driver				
		Impact				

REGION 2: Latin America and the Caribbean						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔	➔	➔	
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Labor & employment	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔	➔	➔	
	Social crises	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Land tenure/ ownership rights	Driver	➔			➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
Demographics	Driver	➔				
	Resource quality & availability	Driver	➔	➔	➔	
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Resource efficiency	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Climate	Impact	➔		➔	
	Trade systems & market dynamics	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Support services & measures	Driver	➔	➔		
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔

APPENDIX G. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN LOCATION GROUPING "REGION 3"

REGION 3: Northern Africa and Western Asia						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver	➔			
	Government support & expenditure	Driver	➔			
	Governance & political environment	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Income & livelihood	Impact	➔			➔
	Food security & nutrition	Impact				➔
	Human rights & well-being	Impact				➔
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔			
	Labor & employment	Impact	➔			
	Land tenure/ Ownership rights	Driver	➔		➔	
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔			
	Resource quality & availability	Driver	➔			
		Impact	➔			➔
	Climate	Driver	➔			

REGION 3: Northern Africa and Western Asia						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
		Impact				
	Support services & measures	Driver				
		Impact				
	Farm economics & resilience	Impact				
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Impact				

APPENDIX H. KEY LINKAGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM – CASE STUDIES WITHIN LOCATION GROUPING "REGION 4"

REGION 4: SubSaharan Africa						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Standards & agreements	Driver	→	→	→	→
	Sustainable policies & regulations	Driver	→	→	→	→
	Government support & expenditure	Driver	→	→	→	→
		Impact	→	→	→	→
	Governance & political environment	Driver	→	→	→	→
		Impact	→	→	→	→
	Income & livelihood	Driver	→	→	→	→
		Impact	→	→	→	→
	Food security & nutrition	Driver	→	→	→	→
		Impact	→	→	→	→
	Financial security	Impact	→	→	→	→
	Human rights & well-being	Driver	→	→	→	→
		Impact	→	→	→	→
	Knowledge & skills	Driver	→	→	→	→

REGION 4: SubSaharan Africa						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
	Community well-being & collaboration	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Social & gender inequalities	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Labor & employment	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Innovative knowledge & good practices	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Land tenure/ Ownership rights	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
Demographics	Driver	➔				
	Resource quality & availability	Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Resource efficiency	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
	Climate	Driver	➔	➔	➔	➔
		Impact	➔	➔	➔	➔

REGION 4: SubSaharan Africa						
DIMENSION	TOPICS	Typology				
		Impact				
	Support services & measures	Driver				
		Impact				
	Macroeconomic factors	Driver				
		Impact				
	Farm economics & resilience	Driver				
		Impact				
	Taxation	Driver				
	Quality standards & competitiveness	Driver				
		Impact				

APPENDIX I. 'TOP TEN' SDGS COVERED IN THE CASE STUDIES

“Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Tanzania”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #1b report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Intra-EU trade, resilience, and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #2 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Trade, sustainability, and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #3 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Enhancing access to export markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) countries through sustainable investments to ensure quality and quantity of agri-food commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #4 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #5 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“The living income differential for cocoa: futures markets and price setting in an unequal value chain”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #6 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“What trade and tax policies are needed for the sustainable development of local milk value chains in West Africa? Proposals to West African and European actors”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #7 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Belgian consumption of sugarcane ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #8 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Risk analysis including stakeholder consultation in the coffee value chain (Uganda - Belgium) of Oxfam België”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #9 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #10 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“The role and impact of production standards: GLOBALG.A.P. certification in Africa”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #11 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #12 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets”

Using a new SDG text mining tool (<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #13 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soy-meat complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #14 report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Markets, power, and potatoes: An analysis of agricultural trade between Egypt and Europe”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #15a report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

“Olive oil and water: Moving towards sustainable agricultural trade between the EU and Tunisia”

Using a new SDG text mining tool

(<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) for the CS #15b report, an extract document of the 'top ten' SDGs covered in the case study can be produced and shown in the following figures:

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH - DASHBOARD

Dashboard:

Use this sheet to navigate through the information presented in this file.
When clicking on a shape, more detailed information on how to complete each table will be shown.

Delivery deadline:
22/12/23 - 15/01/24

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – KEY ATTRIBUTES

<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Dashboard</div>											
1. Key attributes of the CS											
Case Study	N° 1 - A	N° 1 - B	N° 2	N° 3	N° 4	N° 5	N° 6	N° 7	N° 8	N° 9	N° 10
Responsible	John Sumelius	John Sumelius	Bodo Steiner	Nina Hyytiä	Hoseana Lunogelo	Pablo Vidueira	Bart Van Besien	Fairouz Gazdallah	Alba Saray Pérez Terán	Sarah Vaes	Alberto Menghi
Reports											
Title											
Leader partner											
Local partners											
General description CS											
Product											
Market acces (Local, national, international)											
Import markets (Countries)											
Export markets (Countries)											
General objective of the CS (Problematic address)											
Hypothesis /Conjectures											
Methodology used											
Type of data collection											
- Stakeholders involment											
Limitations											
Impact pathways											

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – UNDERSTANDING LINKAGES

Dashboard												
3. Understanding linkages (relevant interactions) along agri-food value chain												
<small>a) Select and specify the element you will report on as a "driver" or an "impact" within the drop-down menus of the "category" column. This selection will activate the options in the drop-down list associated with the "element" column. You can also enter new options if the proposals do not allow you to adequately reflect your case study. b) Provide a concise rationale for your selection and a brief description of the linkage. c) Using the code, rank the degree of influence at each stage of the value chain.</small>												
Dimensions	CS1 - A						CS1 - B					
	Category (Driver / Impact)	Element	Description of the element: How this element is related to the different stages of agri-food trade system?	Degree of influence				Category (Driver / Impact)	Element	Description of the element: How this element is related to the different stages of agri-food trade system?	Degree of influence	
				Agricultural Production	Manufacturing	Trade & Retail	Consumption				Agricultural Production	Manufacturing
Policy, governance & regulation	DriversPG2	Land use policies										
	ImpactsPG2	Governance structures and mechanisms										
Human dimensions							DriversHD2	Livelihoods				
							ImpactsHD2	Poverty rates				
Social dimension	DriversSD2	Social inequalities										
	ImpactsSD2	Employment rates										

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – UNDERSTANDING LINKAGES

		Dashboard						<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Code</th> <th>Explanation</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Fundamentally conditions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Severely affects</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Moderately affects</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Somehow affects</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Does not affect at all</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Code	Explanation	4	Fundamentally conditions	3	Severely affects	2	Moderately affects	1	Somehow affects	0	Does not affect at all
Code	Explanation																				
4	Fundamentally conditions																				
3	Severely affects																				
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<p>a) Select and specify the element you will report on as a "driver" or an "impact" within the drop-down menus of the "category" column. This selection will activate the options in the drop-down list associated with the "element" column. You can also enter new options if the proposals do not allow you to adequately reflect your case study.</p> <p>b) Provide a concise rationale for your selection and a brief description of the linkage.</p> <p>c) Using the code, rank the degree of influence at each stage of the value chain.</p>																					
Dimensions	CS1 - A						CS1 - B														
	Category (Driver / Impact)	Element	Description of the element: How this element is related to the different stages of agri-food trade system?	Degree of influence				Category (Driver / Impact)	Element	Description of the element: How this element is related to the different stages of agri-food trade system?	Degree of influence										
				Agricultural Production	Manufacturing	Trade & Retail	Consumption				Agricultural Production	Manufacturing									
Environmental / Natural capital	ImpactsEN2	Environmental degradation																			
	DriversEN2	Climate change																			
Economy & Market	DriversEM2	Price volatility																			
	ImpactsEM2	Trade economic growth																			
	ImpactsEM2	Competitiveness																			
TOTAL - DRIVERS	4						1														
TOTAL - IMPACTS	5						1														

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – COMMON LIST SDG INDICATORS

		<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 2px 10px; display: inline-block;">Dashboard</div>															
4. Common list of SDGs indicators																	
<i>Mark with an "X"</i>																	
Dimensions	SDG indicators	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4	CS5	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS9	CS10	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS14	CS15	Frequency
Economy & Market	2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status																0
Economy & Market	17.11.1 Developing countries' and least developed countries' share of global exports																0
Economy & Market	2.3.1 Volume of production per labour unit by classes of farming/pastoral/forestry enterprise size																0
Economy & Market	8.5.1 Average hourly earnings of employees, by sex, age, occupation and persons with disabilities																0
Economy & Market	10.a.1 Proportion of tariff lines applied to imports from least developed countries and developing countries with zero-tariff																0
Economy & Market	8.a.1 Aid for Trade commitments and disbursements																0
Economy & Market	17.12.1 Weighted average tariffs faced by developing countries, least developed countries and small island developing States																0
Environmental / Natural capital	15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area																0
Environmental / Natural capital	6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources																0
Environmental / Natural capital	8.4.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP																0
Environmental / Natural capital	8.4.2 Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per GDP																0
Environmental / Natural capital	6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality																0

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – COMMON LIST SDG INDICATORS

		Dashboard															
4. Common list of SDGs indicators																	
Mark with an "X"																	
Dimensions	SDG indicators	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4	CS5	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS9	CS10	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS14	CS15	Frequency
Human dimensions	1.1.1 Proportion of the population living below the international poverty line by sex, age, employment status and geographic location (urban/rural)																0
Human dimensions	2.1.2 Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES)																0
Human dimensions	2.2.2 Prevalence of malnutrition (weight for height >+2 or <-2 standard deviation from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards) among children under 5 years of age, by type (wasting and overweight)																0
Human dimensions	10.2.1 Proportion of people living below 50 per cent of median income, by sex, age and persons with disabilities																0
Human dimensions	2.1.1 Prevalence of undernourishment																0
Human dimensions	16.1.1 Number of victims of intentional homicide per 100,000 population, by sex and age (OR) 16.1.3 [] Proportion of population subjected to (a) physical violence, (b) psychological violence and (c) sexual violence in the previous 12 months																0
Policy, governance & regulation	2.a.2 Total official flows (official development assistance plus other official flows) to the agriculture sector																0
Policy, governance & regulation	2.b.1 Agricultural export subsidies																0
Policy, governance & regulation	2.a.1 The agriculture orientation index for government expenditures																0
Policy, governance & regulation	5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex																0
Policy, governance & regulation	12.7.1 Degree of sustainable public procurement policies and action plan implementation																0
Policy, governance & regulation	16.7.2 Proportion of population who believe decision-making is inclusive and responsive, by sex, age, disability and population group [AND/OR] 16.3.3 Proportion of the population who have experienced a dispute in the past two years and who accessed a formal or informal dispute resolution mechanism, by type of mechanism																0

APPENDIX J. CS GUIDANCE TABLE FOR THE ADOPTION OF THE SYSTEMS APPROACH – COMMON LIST SDG INDICATORS

		<div style="border: 1px solid black; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Dashboard</div>															
4. Common list of SDGs indicators																	
Mark with an "X"																	
Dimensions	SDG indicators	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4	CS5	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS9	CS10	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS14	CS15	Frequency
Social dimension	8.3.1 Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex																0
Social dimension	8.8.2 Level of national compliance with labour rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) based on International Labour Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status																0
Social dimension	5.a.1 (a) Proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land, by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights-bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure																0
Social dimension	8.5.2 Unemployment rate, by sex, age and persons with disabilities																0
Social dimension	10.1.1 Growth rates of household expenditure or income per capita among the bottom 40 per cent of the population and the total population																0
Social dimension	5.2.2 Proportion of women and girls aged 15 years and older subjected to sexual violence by persons other than an intimate partner in the previous 12 months, by age and place of occurrence																0
Social dimension	5.4.1 Proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care work, by sex, age and location																0

APPENDIX K. COMMON REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR MATS CASE STUDIES

Common reporting template for the 15 case studies

(taken from MATS Deliverable 3.1:
<https://zenodo.org/record/8043777>)

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Funded by
the European Union

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101000751.

Common reporting template for the 15 case studies, to be used by each case study

Please follow the length and heading guidelines as per below, i.e., even if you don't have info under certain section sub-headings, please leave these sections blank and do not delete the section headings/ sub-headings (be welcome to comment why certain sections are left blank).

By leaving all sub-section headings visible in the document, it will be easier to harvest information from all case studies for the single case study report that will be generated.

Once you have read the guiding information below each sub-section, please just delete this guiding information, and then enter your information (also under the Appendix, Table 1, below!).

Please send your completed template to Chen and Cintya: chen.qiuzhen@helsinki.fi, cintya.manrique@upm.es

If you have questions send them to bodo.steiner@helsinki.fi

Case #:

Case title:

Lead organization & name of lead contact:

Date:

Executive summary

The executive summary should serve as a concise overview of the case study's key insights into the intricate connections between agri-food trade, sustainability, and human well-being. It should start by setting the stage with a brief contextual backdrop (Section 1 and 2.2), establishing the rationale for the case study, and outlining the core hypotheses or research questions under exploration (Section 2.1).

Following this, it introduces the chosen methodological approach (Section 2.3), highlighting key elements within the political, human, social, environmental, and market-related dimensions and specific interrelations that will be explored within the context of the case study (Section 2.4 and 2.5). The summary should then outline the main findings and their implications, providing a systemic perspective on the role of agricultural trade within the broader sustainability and well-being landscape (Section 3).

To conclude, the executive summary should offer actionable policy recommendations aimed at advancing agri-food trade to better align with the goals of sustainability and human well-being (Section 4).

- the executive summary should be between 5% and maximum 10% length of the length of your entire case study report
- please follow the instructions here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/executivesummary>

(1) Introduction

- provide an introduction that builds on your initial CS description, yet also documents the evolution of your CS, and the connection to other CS (incl. methods grouping with other CS, overlaps on commodities, regions etc. in other CS) and WPs, as part of the process of developing and implementing your CS.
- If the purpose, scope, methodological approach, or SDGs indicators differ from what is stated in the Grant Agreement, please provide a brief rationale behind these changes.
- introduce briefly the objectives and research questions (incl. coverage of indicators, key indicator / sustainability dimension focus - see D3.1., p. 25, Figure 1: <https://zenodo.org/record/8043777>)

Introduce the case study by providing a first picture of the dimensions, elements, and indicators that expect to be addressed and explored to contribute to the ultimate goal of providing a comprehensive in-depth assessment of the interlinkages between agricultural trade, investments, sustainability, and human well-being. Please write this section after using the proposed "[Case Studies Summary Table](#)" to obtain an overview of the scope of each case study from a systemic perspective.

- the introduction should be approximately 10% of your total report.

(2) Objectives and analytical approach

Brief description of specific objectives and methodology used for the case study, including data collection and analysis, following these headings:

2.1. Objectives and scope of the CS

This section outlines the specific objectives and scope of the case study, building upon a literature review (Section 2.2) that should not only provide an overview of the pertinent context but also serve as the foundation for the

formulating the hypothesis, conjectures, or research questions that the case study seeks to validate or explore.

When formulating the specific objectives, it is crucial to explicitly articulate how the case study contributes to developing a systemic understanding of agri-food trade and its linkages with sustainability and human well-being. To articulate this, please consider the following:

- Describe the key elements/features within the political, human, social, environmental, and market-related dimensions deem relevant to your case study.
- Explain the role of those elements in agri-food trade, whether as drivers influencing the agri-food trade system or as impacts resulting from it.
- Describe the key linkages you deem relevant in your case study between the five contextual dimensions and the activities within food systems.
- Select the SDGs indicators that you found relevant for your case study.

The “[Case Studies Summary Table](#)” expects to be instrumental to follow the aforementioned considerations.

2.2. Literature

As described in the previous section, this section aims to play a critical role in establishing the rationale for the case study’s objective, serving as the foundation for formulating the hypothesis, conjectures, or research questions that the case study seeks to validate or explore.

The “Literature review” section plays a critical role in establishing the rationale for the case study’s objectives, serving as the foundation upon which the case study is built. While it is essential to provide context for your case study, it is equally important to strike a balance by offering relevant information without delving into extensive detail that may not directly align with the goals of your case study.

Please highlight the areas within the existing literature where your case study aims to contribute. Discuss how you will build upon, question, or extend previous findings to formulate your hypothesis or conjectures. This will underscore the value of your case study.

- Literature used in the CS, gaps, conjectures / hypotheses arising from the literature and previous studies (grey literature)
- for guidance see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/literaturereview>

2.3. Methods

This section is adaptable to the unique characteristics of each case study, considering the diversity of objectives, scopes, and methodological approaches adopted. However, there are essential aspects that all case studies should report in:

- i. Systemic approach: Common foundation on the five-dimensional analytical framework and the list of elements and linkages summarized in the [Case Studies Summary Table](#).
 - ii. Sources of information: Describe how the information was obtained, specifying whether primary and/or secondary sources were consulted.
 - iii. Stakeholders' engagement: Identify and describe the stakeholders who have been engaged in the case study. Explain the extent and stages of their involvement, highlighting their roles and contributions.
 - iv. Participatory processes: If applicable, outline any participatory processes employed in your case study (i.e., workshops, interviews, discussion groups, etc.). Describe their purpose, participants, and outcomes.
 - v. Methodological approach: Clarify whether your case study adopts a quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods approach. Provide justification for your choice and discuss how it aligns with your objectives.
- importance of a good methodology section, and how to write it: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/methodology>
 - for definitions of design, collection of data and different types of analyses under qualitative methods, please consult Berg (2012), Norman & Lincoln (2000), as summarized here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/qualitative>
 - methods limitations

- vi. Ethical considerations: Ensure that the process followed in each case study prioritizes the strict confidentiality of all personal data and that anonymized data from surveys and interviews is securely stored. This section will be included in the (6) Appendices and should be signed by the CS leader and the local partners.

2.4. Data description

Please use the [Case Study Summary Table](#) to provide a data description.

The Case Study Summary Table comprises five sheets, three of which aim to set the groundwork for case studies to provide a systemic understanding of the linkages between agri-food trade, investment, sustainability, and human well-being. This common framework will serve as a basis for conducting a comparative analysis across all case studies.

Below you will find a description of the purpose and content of the three sheets mentioned above, which will help to establish a systemic view.

- List of elements in the MATS framework: To gain a comprehensive understanding of linkages between agricultural trade, investments, sustainability, and human well-being, this section provides a range of elements to consider as you evaluate linkages across each stage of the agri-food value chain and the five dimensions of the MATS analytical framework.
Clarity in distinguishing between the terms "Driver" and "Impact" is of paramount importance:
 - ✓ Driver: Understood as those elements that affect the food system activities (from production to consumption)
 - ✓ Impact: Understood as those elements that are being affected by the food system activities (from production to consumption)
- Understanding linkages (relevant interactions) along agri-food value chain: Understanding linkages along agri-food value chain: With the aim of providing a systemic understanding of the linkages between agricultural trade, investments, sustainability, and human well-being, please identify those drivers and impacts relevant to your case study and rank the degree of influence that drivers have over the different stages of the value chain, and the value chain stages over different elements within the five dimensions of the MATS analytical framework (impacts).

- ✓ Provide information on the linkages that explain the current situation/ main issues your case study aims to address. We are especially interested in understanding the ways different elements interrelate with each other, not only within the value chain but with the social, human, natural, economic, and political context.
- ✓ Be comprehensive when describing the linkages, letting us know how they affect other elements of the system (e.g., if they are positive or negative).
- Common list of SDGs indicators: Select at least three Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) indicators within each dimension that align with the focus of your case study.

2.5. Data analysis

If you have any question regarding the systemic analysis of agricultural trade within your case study, please contact KNOWLEDGE and UPM teams.

(3) Results, discussion and limitations

for guidance on writing the results, discussion and limitations sections, see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/results>

3.1. Results and discussion

- Include a statement that clarifies possible linkages between the five contextual dimensions – political, human, social, environmental, and market-related – and the agricultural trade system activities (e.g., identifying positive impacts with regard to social indicators, or impacts on environmental indicators, or political drivers affecting the agricultural production). Please use the [Case Study Summary Table](#) as an instrument to build this statement.
- Include here a visual representation and discussion of the case-specific impact pathways: Visualization and identification of key leverage points in agri-food trade/impact system applicable to your CS.

If you have any question, please contact FRAUNHOFER team.

- Include here a description of actors and gender-issues relevant in the context of your CS: key actors with their roles, interests and responsibilities; gender issues; how to address issues of power inequality, participation, and public interests.

If you have any question, please contact MAASTRICHT and OXFAM teams.

- Include here a description and discussion of the role of national and supranational legal and policy frameworks with particular attention paid to the EU and the WTO as applicable (information required for WP4) (optional: to respond to D.2.3. you could prepare a political economy mapping of the different protagonists, including WTO rules, FTA, national authorities, local actors, private sector, donors).

If you have any question, please contact MAASTRICHT team.

- Discuss your individual lessons learned as a research team, also in terms of mutual learning with other CS during workshops etc., synergies encountered with other CS, or unexpected hindrances.

3.2. Limitations

here please also report all biases here that you have encountered / expect to be relevant in the design and implementation of your CS; for possible limitations / biases of the researcher to report on, and for a discussion of possible methodological limitations, see here: <https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/limitations>

(4) Key conclusions and policy recommendations

outline key determinants/topics for each case study shaping future developments and sustainability impacts; ways forward; recommendations on fostering the positive and reducing the negative impacts of agri-food trade (information required by WP5; see Section 2.3.2)

(5) References

your list of references here; please cite consistently in APA format (so that we can then also accumulate all references for the single case study report to be

submitted as DL) - guidance for citation style to be found here:
<https://libguides.usc.edu/writingguide/citingsources>

(6) Appendices

- We are lacking information on INVESTMENTS throughout MATS, in order to contribute to the 'debate' as promised in our GA, as part of our final comprehensive case study report that is to be uploaded in December 2023. Think i.e. that changes in trade policy regimes (requirements on environmental sustainability, social sustainability, etc.) induce changes in production practises, which causes need for changes in investment flows or volumes.

Please complete the following Table 1, below, as much as possible, based on your case study findings.

Consider the following sources just as background information & inspiration for you completing the table:

<https://blogs.worldbank.org/agfood/why-channeling-investment-smallholders-across-africa-key-resilient-future>

<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/africaatlse/2021/04/02/why-substantial-chinese-fdi-is-flowing-into-africa-foreign-direct-investment/>

<https://assets.cdcgroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/18115511/What-is-the-impact-of-investing-in-FA.pdf>

Table 1: information on investments based on evidence from your case study

	YES	NO	Comments from CS leader on why you have indicated YES/ NO
In our case study, investment issues are not relevant/ not addressed			
In our case study, we have evidence that investment gaps into infrastructure are highly relevant for market access (domestic or foreign).			
In our case study, we have evidence that investment gaps with respect to access to credits are highly relevant for market access (domestic or foreign).			
In our case study, we have evidence that the gender gap is important in explaining the investment gap relevant for improving market access (domestic or foreign).			
In our case study, we have evidence that increasing investment into new technologies related to communication (average of past 3 years or current year) has increased market transparency in the value chain (please comment in cases of decreased transparency).			
In our case study, we have evidence that individual smallholder farmers lack			

<p>access to finance that would otherwise enable them to access markets (domestic or foreign).</p>			
<p>In our case study, we have evidence that cooperatives / producer organizations lack access to finance that would otherwise enable them to access markets (domestic or foreign).</p>			
<p>In our case study, we have evidence that (commodity, technology) exports from Europe are making local investments (into local production, processing, marketing, infrastructure) less attractive/ less likely.</p>			
<p>In our case study, we have evidence that investment from (a.) French, (b.) U.S., (c.) Chinese, (d.) other nation's companies makes a major contribution to improving market access. [please specify which countries apply to the right under "yes" – maximum 3]</p>			
<p>In our case, we have evidence that more than 50% of all foreign investments (into local production, processing, marketing, infrastructure) originates from one country (average of past 3 years, or current year). If applicable under "Yes", please specify on the right which one country.</p>			<p>If approximate % is available, please specify.</p>
<p>In our case, we have evidence that new investments (average of past 3 years, or current year) have helped to reduce greenhouse gas emissions</p>			

(in local production, processing, marketing, infrastructure – please specify!). Please comment in cases of increased emissions.			
In our case study we did not find a connection between trade/ market access and investments.			

- To ensure that the process followed in each case study prioritizes the strict confidentiality of all personal data and that anonymized data from surveys and interviews is securely stored.

Please complete the following format for ethical considerations, based on your case study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

N° Case Study:

Title:

The research team has ensured that data management is compliant with the EU's Guidelines on Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). It has ensured that all personal data was treated as strictly confidential and processed in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and ensured that anonymized data from surveys and interviews was securely stored in a safe location at partners' facilities. All interviews were voluntary and based on informed consent; participants were assured confidentiality of all data collected.

Enumerators had a good command of local languages, and English and they were compelled to display honesty and integrity in their behaviours and respect the dignity and self-worth of the respondents including sensitivity about gender.

(Signature of CS leader)

(Signature of the local partner)

4 Annex 1 – References

Berg, B. L. (2001). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. Allyn & Bacon.

Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Sage.

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Issa, T., Chang, V., & Issa, T. (2010). Sustainable Business Strategies and PESTEL Framework. *GSTF International Journal On Computing*, 1 (1), 73-80.
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Strauss, Anselm, & Corbin, Juliet (2014). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 4th ed. URL: <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/basics-of-qualitative-research/book235578>

Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (Vol. 5). sage.
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https://www.academia.edu/13784473/Case_study_research_design_and_methods_4th_ed_Robert_Yin

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